

PREVIOUSLY UNKNOWN PHYSICAL LAW OF ABERRATION OF THE PHYSICAL QUANTITIES OF A BODY MOVING RELATIVE TO THE OBSERVER

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Abstract . A previously unknown physical law of aberration of physical quantities of a body moving relative to an observer, discovered by the author, is presented. In accordance with the law of aberration, the observed (measured using a measuring device) quantities of a body moving relative to the observer are directly proportional to the same true quantities and inversely proportional to a coefficient that depends on the speed of movement. This law is formulated in mathematical form. The law of aberration combines 16 different physical quantities. The law of aberration is confirmed by two experiments. This law is simple in nature. The law of aberration is multifacetedly symmetrical and amazingly beautiful. The discovery of new physical laws is a rather rare and therefore significant event for world science. The last Nobel Prize was awarded to Owen Whillans Richardson for his discovery of a law of physics in 1928, almost a century ago.

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Graphic Annotation

The law of aberration is amazingly beautiful and has many-sided symmetry.
The law combines 16 quantities

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1. Introduction

The discovery of new physical laws is a rather rare event. In the entire history of mankind, about a hundred physical laws have been discovered. Not all of these laws are formulated in mathematical form (the open law of aberration is formulated in mathematical form). One of the last open universally recognized laws at the world level is the "linear law of Kapitsa", discovered by the Soviet academician Pyotr Leonidovich Kapitsa in 1928. In 1978, Petr Leonidovich was awarded the Nobel Prize with the wording not for the discovery of a physical law, but "for fundamental research in the field of low temperature physics."

The Nobel Committee awarded five people for the discovery of four laws of physics (Table 1). James Frank and Gustav Hertz are jointly awarded for discovering the laws of electron-atom collision.

Table 1 - Nobel Prize winners for discovering the laws of physics

Year	Laureate, country	Rationale for the award
1911	Wilhelm Wien (1864-1928), Germany	For discoveries concerning the laws that govern thermal radiation (See Wien's Displacement Law)
1921	Albert Einstein (1879-1955), Germany	For services to theoretical physics and especially for the discovery of the law of the photoelectric effect
1925	James Frank (1882-1964), Germany Gustav Hertz (1887-1975), Germany	For the discovery of the laws of the collision of an electron with an atom
1928	Owen Willans Richardson (1879-1959), UK	For his work on thermionic phenomena, and especially for the discovery of the law that bears his name

The last Nobel Prize was awarded for the discovery of a law of physics in 1928.

Thus, the discovery of universally recognized laws of physics is a rather rare event in science.

Readers are presented with a new previously unknown physical law, called "the law of aberration of the physical quantities of a body moving relative to the observer." This law was discovered by a Russian scientist, Doctor of Technical Sciences. Plyasovskikh A.P. _ in the process of developing the Theory of Aberration, which is confirmed experimentally. For the first time, the law of aberration of the physical quantities of a body moving relative to an observer was published in 2021 [1]. Then, as it was expanded (adding physical quantities obeying the law), this law was published in [2-4]. The most complete exposition of the law of aberration is presented in monographs [5-7].

The essence of the law of aberration of physical quantities is that when measuring a number of physical quantities of a moving body using electromagnetic waves, the measured physical quantities change along with the change in speed, while remaining directly proportional to the same true quantities. The law of aberration is formulated in *mathematical form* . On the one hand,

this law expresses the observed (measured) quantities in terms of the same true quantities, on the other hand, it expresses the true quantities in terms of the observed ones.

Currently, the law of aberration combines $2^4 = 16$ different physical quantities. All quantities included in the law of aberration during their measurement change in the same way when the speed of the body relative to the measuring installation (observer) changes.

The law of aberration is confirmed by two experiments

Conventions

In this paper, we consider such true and observed quantities of the body as:

r is the distance to the material body;

l is the length of the body;

s is the path traveled by the body;

v is the speed of the body;

μ is the pace of the clock located on the body;

Δt is the time interval counted by the clock located on the body;

ν is the frequency of the radiation source located on the body;

ω is the angular speed of rotation of the point along the circumference;

ω' - circular (angular) frequency of rotation of a point along a circle;

n is the frequency of rotation of the point along the circle;

ω^* is the angular velocity of rotation of the body around the axis;

$\omega^{*'} -$ circular (angular) frequency of rotation of the body;

n^* - body rotation frequency;

ω'' - circular frequency of rectilinear oscillations of a material point;

n'' is the frequency of rectilinear oscillations of a material point;

f is the frequency of the periodic process occurring on the body;

Q is the physical quantity of the body (any of the above).

In addition, the notation is used:

c is the speed of light;

v^c - the speed of the body, expressed in fractions of the speed of light,

$$v^c = v/c;$$

tr - (from English true) subscript to denote true quantities, for example v_{tr} (true speed);

obs - (from English observe) subscript to denote observed quantities, for example v_{obs} (observed speed).

The law of aberration in mathematical form

The law of aberration in mathematical form (in one of the options) is as follows

$$Q_{tr} = const.$$

$$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 + \frac{r_{tr}}{c}}$$

where Q_{tr} and Q_{obs} are, respectively, the true and observed quantities of the moving body;

$\dot{r}_{tr}$ is the rate of change of the true distance from the observer to the body r_{tr} (the first derivative with respect to time):

$$\dot{r}_{tr} = \frac{dr_{tr}}{dt}.$$

The inverse expression of the true quantities in terms of the observed quantities has the form

$$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 - \frac{\dot{r}_{obs}}{c}},$$

where $\dot{r}_{obs}$ is the rate of change in the observed distance from the observer to the body r_{obs} (the first derivative with respect to time):

$$\dot{r}_{obs} = \frac{dr_{obs}}{dt}.$$

Note that the true and observed velocities $\dot{r}_{tr}$ differ from each other in these ratios as well. $\dot{r}_{obs}$ They can take both positive (when the body moves away from the observer) and negative (when the body approaches the observer) values.

The physical meaning of the law of aberration is explained in detail below.

2. On the concept of aberration and physical quantities

The meaning of the concept of "aberration of the physical quantities of a body moving relative to the observer" differs from the well-known concept of *aberrations* (image distortions that occur in optical systems), and the concept of *light aberration* (changes in the direction of propagation of light (radiation) when moving from one frame of reference to another). The concept of "aberration of physical quantities of a body moving relative to the observer" has a slightly different meaning, the essence of which can be explained as follows.

2.1. Aberration of the location of a moving body

Consider first the concept of " *aberration of the location of a body moving relative to the observer* ".

Latin word *aberratio* means evasion, removal.

Let from left to right past the observer, located at the origin of the inertial reference system (ISR), a body moves, the speed of which is v comparable to the speed of light c .

Suppose we ourselves are the observer. The body can be, for example, a distant star, which moves with great speed at the edge of our Galaxy. At some point in time, a flash of light occurs on the body. As long as the light moves to the origin where we are, the body will continue to move. At that moment, when the light from the body reaches our eyes, we will see the body at the point where it was at the time of the flash of light on it. In Aberration Theory, this point is called the "observable location of the body" because that is where we see the body when the light from it reaches our eyes (the origin).

Fig. 1.1. Aberration (deviation) of the location of a body moving relative to the observer

However, due to the fact that the light reaches our eyes with a delay due to the finite speed of light, during the movement of light the body has time to move to another place located on the

trajectory of its movement. At the moment when we observe the body at the point of "observed location", in fact it is ahead of this point in the course of its movement. The point where the body is actually located is called the "true location of the body" (Figure 1.1).

It is important to note that the "observed location of the body" is different from the "true location of the body". The deviation of the observed location of the body from its true location is called the aberration of the location of the body (Fig. 1.1). The reasons for the aberration of the location of the body are the delay in the receipt of information about the location of the body to the observer due to the finite speed of light, as well as the movement of the body. If the speed of light were infinite, then there would be no location aberration. At the infinite speed of light, the observer would see the body in the place where it actually is; in this case, the observed location of the body would coincide with the true location.

The observed location of the body always follows the true location, as the tail "follows" the dog. The true location is always ahead of the observed location, and the observed location is always behind the true location.

The amount of aberration (deviation) of the location of the body depends on two parameters: on the speed of the body and on the distance from the observer to the body.

The amount of aberration of a GPS satellite, for example, which is located at an altitude of 20200 km and moves at a linear speed of about 3.9 km / s, is about 260 m. In other words, the position of the GPS satellite observed from the Earth through a telescope is behind its true (calculated) locations more than a quarter of a kilometer away.

The amount of aberration of the Moon, which moves around the Earth at a speed of about 1.02 km/s, is about 1.3 km. In other words, when we observe the Moon with our own eyes, we see it not where it actually is, but slightly behind, with an offset of 1.3 km.

When observing stars located on the periphery of the galaxy from the center of our galaxy, the Milky Way, the magnitude of the aberration in the location of stars can reach billions of kilometers.

Thus, *the aberration of the location of a moving body* is the deviation of the observed (measured) location of a body moving relative to the observer from its true location, which occurs due to the movement of the body relative to the observer and the delay in the receipt of information about the body by the observer (final speed of light).

2.2. Aberration of the distance from the observer to the moving body

One of the physical quantities of a body moving relative to an observer is the distance from the observer to the location of the body. When a body moves at speeds that are insignificant compared to the speed of light, the true and observed location of the body coincide with each other. But when a body moves at a speed comparable to the speed of light, the observed location of the body follows its true location at a considerable distance.

So, when a body moves towards the observer at a speed of $0.5 c$, where c is the speed of light, the observed location of the body is twice as far from the observer as its true location. If the speed of the body towards the observer is $0.75 c$, the body's observed location is four times further away than its true location.

Naturally, the idea comes to consider such concepts as *the true distance and the observed distance* from the observer to the body, which can differ from each other by several times, tens, thousands and even millions of times (at speeds close to the speed of light).

Let's call *the true distance* to the body the distance from the observer to the true location of the body, and *the observed distance* - the distance from the observer to the observed location of the body (Fig. 1.2).

Fig. 1.2. Observed and true distance to a moving body

We give the following definition.

Aberration of the distance to a moving body is a change in the observed distance to a moving body compared to the true distance to it (Fig. 1.3).

What distance to the body can be measured: observed or true?

With the use of any means of measurement based on electromagnetic waves, for example, using a laser range finder, only the observed distance to a moving body can be measured. If we measure the distance to a moving body using a radar or a laser range finder, then at the moment when the electromagnetic pulse reflected from the body comes back, the measuring tool receives information about the range with a delay equal to the time the electromagnetic pulse travels from the body to the radar or laser range finder. An electromagnetic pulse brings information about *the observed* distance to the body. During the time that the electromagnetic pulse moved from the body, this body moves to another place, to the point of the true location of the body.

Knowing the observed distance to the body, which is measured using any means of measurement, we can also calculate the true distance to the body. For calculations, you need to know the formula that relates the true distance to the body with the observed distance.

Fig. 1.3. Distance aberration to a body moving relative to the observer

2.3. Aberration of the speed of a moving body

One of the most interesting effects of the Theory of Aberration is the aberration of the speed of a moving body.

We will call *the true speed* of the body the speed of movement of the true location of the body and, accordingly, *the observed speed* - the speed of movement of the observed location of the body (Fig. 1.4).

With the exception of the case of uniform motion of the body along a circle, in the center of which the observer is located, the observed speed of the body's movement differs from its true speed.

The deviation of the observed speed of the body from its true speed is called *the aberration of the speed of the body*.

Fig. 1.4. Aberration of body speed

It is easy to prove (a rigorous proof will be given below) that the observed and true speed of the body are related to each other in the same way as the observed and true distance to the body are related.

$$\frac{\text{Observed speed}}{\text{True speed}} = \frac{\text{Observed distance}}{\text{True distance}}$$

The observed speed of a body is directly proportional to its true speed:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Observed speed} &= \\ &= \text{True Speed} \times \frac{\text{Observed Distance}}{\text{True Distance}} = \\ &= \text{True Speed} \times \text{Proportional factor} \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to prove this relation. Let's consider a special case. Let's imagine that a spaceship started from the Earth to a distant star at a speed equal to the speed of light. Suppose we observe it using radar. During the time that the electromagnetic pulse of the radar, reflected from the starship, will move towards the Earth, the starship will move from its observed location to the true location (Fig. 1.5).

Fig. 1.5. The movement of a starship from the Earth at the speed of light. The starship's observed location is twice as close as its true location, its observed speed is half its true speed.

Since the speed of the spaceship is equal to the speed of light, the magnitude of the aberration (displacement) of the location of the spaceship is equal to the observed distance to the spaceship. In other words, while the light travels the distance from the observed location of the starship to the Earth, the starship has time to move (at the speed of light) exactly the same distance. In this case, the true distance to the starship is twice the observed distance.

In order to cover the "true distance" (Fig. 1.5), from the moment of launch, the starship took a certain time. But during the same time, the starship's observed location moved away from Earth by an "observed distance" that is half its true position. In other words, during the same flight time, the observed location point has moved from the Earth by the observed distance, and the true location point has moved from the Earth by the true distance.

That's why

$$\text{Observed speed} = \frac{\text{Observed distance}}{\text{Movement time}}$$

$$\text{True Speed} = \frac{\text{True Distance}}{\text{Movement time}}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{Observed distance}}{\text{Observed speed}} &= \frac{\text{True distance}}{\text{True speed}} = \\ &= \text{Movement time} \end{aligned}$$

It follows that observed speed is related to true speed in the same way that observed distance is related to true distance:

$$\frac{\text{Observed speed}}{\text{True speed}} = \frac{\text{Observed distance}}{\text{True distance}}$$

Corollary 1 . When a body moves away from the observer, its observed speed is less than the true speed, just as the observed distance from the observer to the body is less than the true distance to it.

Consequence 2 . When the body moves towards the observer, its observed speed is greater than the true speed, since the observed distance from the observer to the body is greater than the true distance to it.

It is interesting to note that when the true speed of the body is equal to half the speed of light, *the observed speed of the body* moving towards the observer becomes equal to the speed of light. When the true speed of the body is greater than half the speed of light, *the observed speed of the body* moving towards the observer becomes *superluminal* .

For example, if the true speed of an asteroid towards the Earth is $0.75 c$, we will record with the help of observation tools that this asteroid is moving towards us at a speed four times the speed of light!

The possibility of motion of bodies with superluminal true and observed speed is discussed in detail in [1, 5] and other works.

2.4. Aberration of physical quantities of a moving body

We have shown that when considering such physical quantities of a moving body as the distance from the observer to the body, and its speed, there is an aberration of these quantities, that is, a deviation of the observed (measured) values of the body from the true (calculated) values. An analysis of some other physical quantities of a moving body shows that in the case of remote measurement of these quantities using an electromagnetic field (and other fields) that propagates at a finite speed of light, the same phenomenon of aberration of the measured physical quantities occurs.

In other words, the values of the measured physical quantities of the body when it moves relative to the observer (measuring installation) change with the change in speed.

In this case, it turns out that the nature of the change in a number of physical quantities of the body is the same and is described by a formula that is identical in appearance. The general pattern of changes in a number of physical quantities of a body depending on the speed of the body is called " *the law of aberration of the physical quantities of a body moving relative to the observer* " .

Definition. *An aberration of the physical quantities of a moving body* is a change in the observed (measured) physical quantities of the body and the processes occurring on it compared to the same true quantities, which occurs due to the movement of the body relative to the observer and the delay in the receipt of information about the body by the observer (final speed of light).

2.5. Illustration of the law of aberration

Let us illustrate the law of aberration with the following example. Let's assume that we are observing through a telescope (hypothetically) a rotating asteroid, the rotation frequency of which is 1 revolution per second. On the asteroid there is a clock with a huge dial, and we can observe the readings of this clock. The asteroid also has a transmitter of electromagnetic waves with a frequency of 1 Hz. Let there also be devices on the asteroid that measure the parameters of the asteroid's motion and transmit them to the earth. These devices can, in particular, measure the true frequency of rotation of the asteroid.

It turns out that the observed rotation frequency of an asteroid at the same true rotation frequency depends on its speed of movement towards us.

At a speed of approach to the Earth equal to 0.5 c , the observed frequency of rotation of the asteroid (with a true rotation frequency of 1 revolution per second) will be equal to 2 revolutions per second. At a speed of approach to the Earth equal to 0.9 c , the observed frequency of rotation of the asteroid will be equal to 10 revolutions per second. If the asteroid were moving away from us at the speed of light, its observed rotation rate would be 0.5 revolutions per second.

Formula for the observed asteroid rotation frequency n_{obs}^* looks like:

when an asteroid approaches us:

$$n_{obs}^* = \frac{n_{tr}^*}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (1.1a)$$

when the asteroid moves away from us:

$$n_{obs}^* = \frac{n_{tr}^*}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (1.1b)$$

where n_{tr}^* is the true rotation frequency of the asteroid;

v_{tr} is the true speed of the body.

Surprising is the fact that not only the observed frequency of rotation of the asteroid obeys the law (1.1), but also 15 other quantities of the asteroid!

The following changes according to the same law: the observed distance from the Earth to the asteroid, the observed path traveled by the asteroid, the observed dimensions of the asteroid (along the line of motion), its observed speed, the time interval measured from the observed clock readings on the asteroid, the accepted frequency of electromagnetic waves, and others.

The law of aberration of the physical quantities of a moving body expresses the same nature of the change in 16 observed quantities of the body with a change in the speed of the body.

3. The law of aberration of physical quantities

3.1. Doppler effect

To understand further material, we present well-known information about the Doppler effect.

The Doppler effect is a physical phenomenon, according to which the frequency of oscillations perceived by the observer changes when the source of oscillations and the observer move relative to each other [8].

Let a transmitter moving towards a fixed receiver broadcast electromagnetic waves, for example, with a true frequency $\nu_{tr} = 100$ Hz. In this case, exactly one wave is transmitted in $1/100$ of a second, and 100 waves are transmitted in 1 second.

In accordance with the Doppler effect, the receiver will record electromagnetic waves with a different frequency. In the case of the transmitter moving towards the receiver, the frequency of the received electromagnetic waves will be equal (Fig. 3.1)

$$\nu_{obs} = \frac{\nu_{tr}}{1 - \frac{\nu_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.1a)$$

where ν_{tr} is the speed of the transmitter to the receiver;
 c is the speed of light.

Fig. 3.1. Doppler effect. The movement of the transmitter to the receiver

At a non-zero speed of movement ν_{tr} , according to the Doppler effect, an increase in the frequency of reception of electromagnetic waves will be observed, that is, the received (observed) frequency will be greater than 100 Hz. And this means that more than 100 waves will be received in 1 second. In other words, when the transmitter moves towards the receiver $\nu_{obs} > \nu_{tr}$.

In the case of movement of the transmitter from a stationary receiver, the relation will take place

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.1b)$$

In accordance with this expression, the received frequency of electromagnetic waves will be less than the frequency of transmitted waves, $v_{obs} < v_{tr}$.

In general, the formula for the Doppler effect (when the transmitter moves along the line connecting the transmitter and receiver) can be written as follows:

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.1c)$$

where the plus sign in the denominator is when the transmitter moves away from the receiver; minus sign - when it approaches the receiver.

Where do the "extra" waves come from? How can it happen that 100 waves are transmitted per second (hours of the transmitter), and 200 waves are received per second (hours of the receiver), at a speed equal to half the speed of light?

This is easy to understand on the example of sea waves. Let's imagine that we are on the seashore, on which waves roll with a frequency of 10 waves per minute. But now imagine that we got on a jet ski and rushed towards the waves. Obviously, now the crests of the waves will be reached by us more often than 10 times per minute. There were already waves ("superfluous"), only as a result of our movement we began to reach each next wave faster, compared to if we were standing motionless on the shore.

If we imagine a mechanical wave generator on the smooth surface of a quiet lake, which moves at some speed from one shore to another, then we will see that in front of this generator the waves are located more often, the crests of the waves are closer to each other than behind the generator. Waves in front of the moving generator will hit the shore in the direction of travel more often than waves behind the generator. The "extra" waves that have reached the front (in the direction of the generator) coast have already been generated. Simply because of the movement of the generator, they are closer to each other (compared to if the generator remained stationary), and accordingly reach the front bank more often.

An approximately similar picture is observed when the transmitter of electromagnetic waves moves relative to the receiver: "extra" waves have already been generated, but they began to reach the receiver due to the movement of the transmitter more often compared to if the transmitter was stationary.

Note that the Doppler effect follows directly from the principle of location aberration of a transmitter moving relative to a receiver.

3.2 . Relationship between observed and true quantities of rotation

Consider the rotational motion of a material point around the center of rotation.

Angular velocity

Angular velocity is a vector quantity that characterizes the speed and direction of rotation of a material point or an absolutely rigid body relative to the axis of rotation. The module of angular velocity for rotational motion coincides with the instantaneous angular frequency of rotation.

Let the material point P rotate uniformly around a circle of radius A with a constant angular velocity ω_{tr} (Fig. 3.2).

Fig. 3.2. Rotation of a material point around the center O

The angular velocity ω_{tr} for uniform rotation is equal to the derivative of the angle of rotation φ_{tr} by time

$$\omega_{tr} = \frac{d\varphi_{tr}}{dt}.$$

In accordance with this, the angle of rotation of the material point in time t is equal to $\varphi_{tr} = \omega_{tr}t$.

N projection material point P on the diameter, for example, on the X axis, will oscillate from the extreme position N_1 to the other extreme position N_2 and back. Such an oscillation of the point N is called simple or harmonic oscillation.

x - coordinate points N is defined by the expression

$$x = A \cos(\varphi(t)) = A \cos(\omega_{tr}t + \delta),$$

where δ is the angle between the X axis and radius OP at the initial time $t = 0$.

Angle $\varphi(t)$ between X axis and radius OP at time t equals

$$\varphi(t) = \omega_{tr}t + \delta.$$

Circular frequency

Circular or angular frequency (synonyms: radial frequency, cyclic frequency) is a scalar physical quantity, a measure of the frequency of rotational or oscillatory motion. In the case of rotational motion, the angular frequency is equal to the modulus of the angular velocity vector. The angular frequency in the SI and CGS systems is expressed in radians per second, its dimension is the reciprocal of the dimension of time (radians are dimensionless).

The circular frequency ω' is related to the rotational speed n by the ratio

$$\omega' = 2\pi n.$$

Consider the observation of a rotating material point P around the circumference. The true speed (or the ratio of the number of revolutions to the time) is equal to n_{tr} . Let an emitter of electromagnetic oscillations be located near the rotating point P , and the oscillation frequency ν_{tr} is equal to the rotation frequency, $\nu_{tr} = n_{tr}$. The rotation of the material point occurs synchronously with the transmission of electromagnetic waves.

We will assume that the rotation of a material point (Fig. 3.3) is followed by an observer who is located on the axis of rotation and is at a considerable distance from the center of rotation O . In other words, the observer's axis of vision (observation) is perpendicular to the plane of rotation of the material point. An observer using a receiver fixes the frequency of the received electromagnetic oscillations. Since the rotation of the material point is carried out synchronously with the transmission of electromagnetic waves, the observed rotation of the material point will be synchronous with the received (observed) electromagnetic wave (Fig. 3.3). The conclusion about the synchronism of the observed rotation and the observed electromagnetic waves follows from the fact that information about the rotation of a material point (when it is observed) and electromagnetic waves propagate with the same speed of light c .

Fig. 3.3. The rotation of a material point and the transmission of electromagnetic waves are carried out synchronously. Due to the fact that information about the rotation of a material point and electromagnetic waves propagate at the same speed of light c , the observed rotation of the material point and the electromagnetic waves observed (perceived) by the receiver will be synchronous

It is obvious, therefore, that by virtue of (3.1) the following relations will hold.

When approaching the center of rotation O to the observer

$$n_{obs} = \frac{n_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.2a)$$

when the center of rotation moves away from the observer

$$n_{obs} = \frac{n_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.2b)$$

where n_{tr} and n_{obs} are, respectively, the true frequency and the frequency of rotation perceived by the observer.

In general

$$n_{obs} = \frac{n_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.2c)$$

When approaching the center of rotation O to the observer, the observer, firstly, in accordance with the Doppler effect, will fix an increase in the perceived frequency of electromagnetic oscillations, and secondly, exactly the same (due to the fact that the transmission of electromagnetic oscillations and the rotation of a point occur synchronously) an increase in the observed rotational frequency of a material point.

When the center of rotation O from the observer, he will record a decrease in the perceived frequency of electromagnetic oscillations, and exactly the same decrease in the observed rotational frequency of a material point.

Since $\omega'_{tr} = 2\pi\nu_{tr} = 2\pi n_{tr}$, it follows from relations (3.1) and (3.2) that as the center of rotation O to the observer

$$\omega'_{obs} = \frac{\omega'_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.3a)$$

when the center of rotation moves away from the observer

$$\omega'_{obs} = \frac{\omega'_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.3b)$$

where ω'_{tr} and ω'_{obs} are, respectively, the true circular frequency and the circular rotational frequency perceived by the observer.

In general

$$\omega'_{obs} = \frac{\omega'_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.3c)$$

The physical meaning of formulas (3.3) is as follows. If the center of rotation O material point P will move towards the observer, then the observer will fix the increase in the angular frequency of rotation in accordance with the formula (3.3a). So, for example, if an observer follows ω'_{tr} a disk of a circular saw rotating with an angular frequency, the plane of which is perpendicular to the axis of vision, and this disk approaches him, then the observer will fix that the angular frequency of rotation of the disk approaching him ω'_{obs} has increased in accordance with the expression (3.3a). The observed angular frequency of rotation of the disk approaching the observer is greater than the true angular frequency of rotation of this disk, $\omega'_{obs} > \omega'_{tr}$.

If the center of rotation O material point P will move away from the observer, then the observer will record a decrease in the angular frequency of rotation in accordance with the formula (3.3 b). In other words, if the observed rotating disk of a circular saw moves away from the observer, then the observed angular frequency of rotation of the disk will be less than the true angular frequency of rotation, $\omega'_{obs} < \omega'_{tr}$.

Since the circular (angular) rotation frequency of the point ω' is equal to the modulus of the angular velocity ω vector, then the observed angular velocity of the point ω_{obs} is related to the true angular velocity of the point ω_{tr} by formulas similar to (3.3)

when approaching the center of rotation O to the observer

$$\omega_{obs} = \frac{\omega_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.4a)$$

when the center of rotation moves away from the observer

$$\omega_{obs} = \frac{\omega_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.4b)$$

in general

$$\omega_{obs} = \frac{\omega_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.4c)$$

Observation of a rotating body

Let the observer consider a rotating body moving towards him or away from him. This body can be, for example, a hypothetical rotating asteroid, which is followed by an astronomer with a telescope.

If ω_{tr}^* is the true angular velocity of rotation of the body around an axis coinciding with the line connecting the center of mass of the body and the observer, then when the body moves towards the observer, the observed angular velocity of rotation of the body ω_{obs}^* is determined by the formula:

$$\omega_{obs}^* = \frac{\omega_{tr}^*}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.5a)$$

The observed angular velocity of rotation of the body ω_{obs}^* as the body moves away from the observer is:

$$\omega_{obs}^* = \frac{\omega_{tr}^*}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.5b)$$

In general

$$\omega_{obs}^* = \frac{\omega_{tr}^*}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.5c)$$

where the plus sign in the denominator is when the body moves away from the observer; minus sign - when it approaches the observer.

It is also obvious that the observed body rotation frequency n_{obs}^* is determined by the formulas:

when the body approaches the observer:

$$n_{obs}^* = \frac{n_{tr}^*}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.6a)$$

when the body moves away from the observer:

$$n_{obs}^* = \frac{n_{tr}^*}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.6b)$$

in general:

$$n_{obs}^* = \frac{n_{tr}^*}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.6c)$$

where n_{tr}^* is the true frequency of rotation of the body;

the plus sign in the denominator - when the body moves away from the observer; minus sign - when it approaches the observer.

Observation of rectilinear harmonic oscillations of a material point

Consider a rectilinear horizontal motion of a material point of mass m along a fixed smooth plane under the action of the elastic force of the spring [9, p. 256-258].

In this case, the horizontal coordinate x of the point can be described by the equation

$$x = A \cos(\omega''_{tr} t - \varphi_0),$$

where A is the largest deviation x of the point from the equilibrium position, called the oscillation amplitude;

φ_0 - initial phase;

ω''_{tr} - true circular frequency, equal to the number of oscillations in 2π seconds.

The true circular frequency ω''_{tr} and the true oscillation frequency n''_{tr} are related by the formula

$$\omega''_{tr} = 2\pi n''_{tr}.$$

The true oscillation frequency n''_{tr} is the number of oscillations per second, the unit of frequency is hertz.

As in the previous cases, it can be shown that in the case of observation of rectilinear harmonic oscillations of a material point, the relations

when approaching the equilibrium position of the point to the observer

$$\omega''_{obs} = \frac{\omega''_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.7a)$$

when the equilibrium position of the point is removed from the observer:

$$\omega''_{obs} = \frac{\omega''_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.7b)$$

in general:

$$\omega''_{obs} = \frac{\omega''_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.7c)$$

where ω''_{obs} and ω''_{tr} are, respectively, the observed and true circular frequency of rectilinear harmonic oscillations of a material point;

the plus sign in the denominator - when the equilibrium position of the point is removed from the observer; minus sign - when it approaches the observer.

The following relations take place in a similar way:

when approaching the equilibrium position of the point to the observer

$$n''_{obs} = \frac{n''_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.8a)$$

when the equilibrium position of the point is removed from the observer:

$$n''_{obs} = \frac{n''_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.8b)$$

in general:

$$n''_{obs} = \frac{n''_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.8c)$$

where n''_{obs} and n''_{tr} are, respectively, the observed and true frequency of rectilinear harmonic oscillations of a material point;

the plus sign in the denominator - when the equilibrium position of the point is removed from the observer; minus sign - when it approaches the observer.

When observing vertical oscillations of a load of mass m on a vertical spring [ibid., p. 259] the equations relating the observed and true circular frequencies and frequencies of harmonic oscillations are similar.

Some consequences. The observed rotation of the hands on the dial of a clock moving relative to the observer.

Imagine an observer watching the hands of a clock whose dial is perpendicular to the axis connecting the observer and the center of the dial. Based on formula (3.2a), we can conclude that if the observed clock moves towards the observer, then the observed angular velocity of rotation of their hands will increase compared to their true angular velocity. In other words, the clock moving towards the observer in exact accordance with (3.2a) according to observations will go *faster* than exactly the same stationary clock. While one second will pass according to a stationary clock located next to the observer, v_{tr} seconds (more than a second) will pass according to the observed readings approaching him at the speed of the same clock $\cdot \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$

Accordingly, when the observed clock moves away from the observer in accordance with formula (3.2 b), the observed angular velocity (and frequency) of rotation of the hands will decrease. According to observations, a clock moving away from the observer will go slower than the same stationary clock located next to the observer. While one second passes by a stationary clock, seconds (less than a second) will pass by the observed readings of a clock moving away from the observer $\cdot \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$

3. 3. Relationship between observed and true distance to a moving body

Let us derive a formula expressing the dependence of the observed distance to a moving body on the true distance to this body.

Consider the motion of a material point in the IFR, at the origin O of which is an observer with a clock. Let the point move towards the observer with a speed v_{tr} along the line connecting the point and the observer. The subscript " tr " is used here to denote *true* speed, which is the usual speed of classical mechanics.

Let the observer continuously observe the location of the point (or, equivalently, measure the distance to the point and the azimuth of the point) using the so-called primary surveillance radar, the principle of which is to detect the reflection of transmitted radio emission pulses.

Let the radio emission pulse from the radar antenna be transmitted in the direction of the observed point at time τ_0 , reflected from the point at time τ_1 , and returned back to the radar at time τ_2 .

It's obvious that

$$\tau_1 = \frac{\tau_0 + \tau_2}{2},$$

and the distance to the point, measured using the transmitted and received reflected pulses, is

$$r_{obs} = \frac{\tau_2 - \tau_0}{2} c = (\tau_2 - \tau_1) c = \Delta t \cdot c, \quad (3.9)$$

where c is the speed of light.

In this expression, the quantity $\Delta t = \tau_2 - \tau_1$ represents the time of movement of the reflected impulse from the observed material point to the observer.

At the moment of reception of the pulse reflected from the observed point, τ_2 the observer observes (sees on the radar indicator) a point at a distance r_{obs} .

However, from the moment of reflection of the impulse from the point τ_1 to the moment of observation, τ_2 the time interval has passed $\Delta t = \tau_2 - \tau_1$, during which the point with the speed v_{tr} from the observed location M_{obs} has moved to a distance $\Delta r = v_{tr} \Delta t = v_{tr} (\tau_2 - \tau_1)$, or taking into account (3.9):

$$\Delta r = \frac{v_{tr}}{c} r_{obs}. \quad (3.10)$$

In other words, at the moment τ_2 of observing a material point at a point in space M_{obs} , the true location of the material point is at point M_{tr} . Let's call the point (of space) M_{obs} at which the material point is observed, *the observed* location of the material point, and the point M_{tr} - its *true* location (Fig. 3.4).

Fig. 3.4. Approaching the observer of a material point observed with the help of a radar. The observed location of a point is further than the true location

Distance between observed and true locations of a material point $|M_{obs}M_{tr}| = \Delta r = \frac{v_{tr}}{c} r_{obs}$ will be called *the value of the aberration of the location* of the material point.

Distance $|OM_{tr}| = r_{tr}$ represents *the true distance* to the material point (Fig. 3.4). Accordingly, the distance from the observer to the observed location of the point $|OM_{obs}| = r_{obs}$ will be called *the observed distance* to the point.

Let us write down the obvious from Fig. 3.4 ratio:

$$|OM_{tr}| + |M_{tr}M_{obs}| = |OM_{obs}|$$

or

$$r_{tr} + \Delta r = r_{obs},$$

whence, taking into account (3.10), it is easy to obtain:

$$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.11a)$$

In accordance with (3.11a), the observed distance to a point approaching the observer is always greater than the true distance. This is explained by the fact that during the time that the reflected pulse from the point moved to the origin, the point also moved a distance Δr .

Consider also the motion of a material point away from the observer (Fig. 3.5).

At the moment τ_2 of observation of a material point at the location, M_{obs} the material point, moving away from the observer with a speed v_{tr} , will move to the location M_{tr} . As in the previous case, the distance $|OM_{tr}| = r_{tr}$ is *the true distance* to the material point, $|OM_{obs}| = r_{obs}$ is *the observed distance*, $\Delta r = |M_{tr}M_{obs}|$ is the distance between the observed and the true location of the point:

$$\Delta r = \frac{v_{tr}}{c} r_{obs}.$$

Fig. 3.5. The movement of a material point observed with the help of a radar from an observer. The observed location of a point is closer than the true location

From fig. 3.5 follows:

$$|OM_{tr}| = |OM_{obs}| + |M_{tr}M_{obs}|$$

or

$$r_{tr} = r_{obs} + \Delta r,$$

whence we obtain a relation similar to (3.11a):

$$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.11b)$$

In accordance with this expression, the observed distance to a point moving away from the observer is always less than the true distance. This is due to the fact that during the time of movement of the reflected pulse from the point to the origin, the point also moved and moved further from the observer (at a distance Δr).

Given the same form (3.11a) and (3.11 b), we obtain the ratio between the observed and true distance to a moving material point in general form:

$$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.11c)$$

where the plus sign in the denominator is when the point is removed from the observer; minus sign - when it approaches the observer.

Let's consider some particular cases.

When a material point moves towards the observer at a speed of $0.5 c$ (half the speed of light) in accordance with (3.11a), the true location of the point will be 2 times closer than the observed location. At a speed of $0.99 c$, the material point will be observed at a distance 100 times greater than it actually is.

When a material point moves away from the observer at a speed close to the speed of light, according to (3.11 b), the true location of the point will be almost 2 times further than its observed location.

Relationship between observed and true distance to a material point

Let us note here that the Doppler effect (according to which, when the source of oscillations moves relative to the observer, there is a change in the frequency of oscillations perceived by the observer) is described by relations (3.1), similar to (3.11).

That is why the observed and true distance to a moving material point are quantitatively and qualitatively related to each other in the same way as the frequency perceived by the observer (receiver) and the frequency of the source of oscillations are related to each other.

The same form of expressions for the Doppler effect (3.1), as well as (3.11) gives reason to assume that both the Doppler effect and the effect of aberration (change) of the observed distance from the observer to the material point compared to the true distance expressed by formulas (3.11) have the same physical nature and are determined, in essence, by the same physical causes.

Note that formulas (3.11), expressing the relationship between the observed and true distance from the observer to the moving material point, are not a consequence of the Doppler effect. These formulas are not derived from the Doppler effect formulas (3.1), at least the author does not know how to derive formulas (3.11) from formulas (3.1).

3. 4. The relationship between the observed and true speed of a moving body

Let us derive a formula expressing the dependence of the observed speed of a moving body on its true speed.

Consider the movement of a material point towards the observer (Fig. 3.4). Relations (3.11) take place in the speed range v_{tr} from 0 to the speed of light. From formula (3.11a)

$$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$$

it follows that when the true distance r_{tr} is equal to zero, the observed distance r_{obs} is also equal to zero. It follows that the observed location of a material point M_{obs} moves towards the observer with an observed speed v_{obs} , which is greater than the true speed of movement v_{tr} (true speed v_{tr} is the speed of movement of the true location M_{tr} of the material point; observed speed v_{obs} is the speed of movement of the observed location of M_{obs} the point).

Fig. 3.6. The observed and true location of a material point as it moves towards the observer at various points in time. Observed movement speed v_{obs} more true speed v_{tr}

On fig. 3.6 shows the movement of a material point towards the observer with a true speed v_{tr} equal to 0.5 of the speed of light. At this speed, the observed location of the point M_{obs} is exactly 2 times farther than the true location M_{tr} . The figure shows the true and observed location of the point at different moments (slices) of time: $t_0, t_1, \dots, t_6$. From fig. 3.6 it can be seen that over a period of time $\Delta t = t_6 - t_0$ the movement of the observed location M_{obs} is exactly 2 times the movement of the true location M_{tr} . This means that the observed speed of movement of a material point v_{obs} is exactly 2 times higher than the true speed of movement v_{tr} (for this example, at $v_{tr} = 0.5 c$).

True and observed speeds of movement of a material point and their relationship

Let us consider the IFR, at the origin O of which is the observer and the clock.

Fig. 3.7. Approach of a material point to a stationary observer at the origin of coordinates

Let a material point move along the X axis to the observer located at the origin of coordinates so that the y and z coordinates of the point are equal to zero (Fig. 3.7). Let also along the X axis at the points A and B , at a distance from the observer r_1^{tr} and r_2^{tr} respectively, other fixed observers are located, each with its own clock. The clocks of all observers are fixed and synchronized with each other.

Let also the observers on the x -axis (located at points A and B) fix the time moments of the material point passing by them t_1 and t_2 and transmit information about the time of passage of the material point points in space A and B (that is, past them) to the observer at the origin of coordinates (for example, using radio communication).

It was shown above that at the moment when the moving material point is in the true location A , its observed (by the observer at the origin) location is located farther from the observer, at the point E , the distance of which is r_1^{obs} , and in accordance with (3.11)

$$r_1^{obs} = \frac{r_1^{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.12)$$

Similarly, when a material point passes a point B (true location), its observed location will be at a point F whose distance is r_2^{obs} , while

$$r_2^{obs} = \frac{r_2^{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.13)$$

It is obvious that the speed of movement of the true location of the material point, which is called *the true speed*, is equal to

$$v_{tr} = \frac{r_1^{tr} - r_2^{tr}}{t_2 - t_1}, \quad (3.14)$$

where r_1^{tr} and r_2^{tr} is the true distance from the observer at the origin to the approaching material point at times t_1 and t_2 respectively.

It is also obvious that the speed of movement of the observed location of the material point, that is, *the observed speed*, is determined as follows:

$$v_{obs} = \frac{r_1^{obs} - r_2^{obs}}{t_2 - t_1}, \quad (3.15)$$

where r_1^{obs} and r_2^{obs} are the observed distance from the observer at the origin of coordinates to the approaching material point at times t_1 and t_2 respectively.

Substituting (3.12) and (3.13) into expression (3.15) for the observed speed v_{obs} , we get:

$$v_{obs} = \frac{r_1^{obs} - r_2^{obs}}{t_2 - t_1} = \left(\frac{r_1^{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} - \frac{r_2^{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \right) \frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \frac{r_1^{tr} - r_2^{tr}}{t_2 - t_1},$$

whence, taking into account (3.14), we obtain:

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.16a)$$

Making similar calculations for the case of the removal of a material point from the observer, we can obtain that

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.16b)$$

and in general:

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.16c)$$

where the plus sign in the denominator is when the point is removed from the observer; minus sign - when it approaches the observer.

From (3.16) it is easy to derive inverse relations in which the true speed v_{tr} is expressed in terms of the observed speed v_{obs} :

when the point approaches the observer:

$$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.17a)$$

(here, in contrast to (3.16a), the denominator has a plus sign);

when the point is moved away from the observer:

$$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.17b)$$

(here, in contrast to (3.16 b), the denominator has a minus sign);

in general:

$$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.17c)$$

where the minus sign is when the material point is moving away, and the plus sign is when it approaches the observer. The signs in the denominator of expressions (3.17), as compared to expressions (3.16), are inverted (they are set "on the contrary").

Surprisingly, the expressions (3.16) and (3.17) are symmetrical in many respects, that is, they are mathematically beautiful. We will speak about the beauty of the law of aberration below.

Note that the Doppler effect formulas (3.1), relations (3.11), connecting the observed and true distance to a point, as well as relations (3.16), describing the relationship between the observed and true speed of the point, are identical; this suggests that the described phenomena have a related (identical) physical nature.

Let's consider special cases.

From (3.16a) it follows that if a material point (for example, a star observed in a telescope) moves towards the Earth at the speed of $v_{tr} = 0,9$ light, then its observed speed v_{obs} will be 10 times greater, that is, on the screen of a hypothetical radar, we will see it moving with at a speed of $9c$, or at a speed 9 times the speed of light.

If the star is moving towards the Earth with the true speed $v_{tr} = 0,999c$, then the observed speed of its movement will exceed the speed of light by 999 times! In other words, we will see (observe) the star that will move towards us with such a true speed with the help of a telescope, for example, approaching us at a speed equal to 999 speeds of light.

When a material point moves away from the observer with a true speed equal to $0,999c$, in accordance with (3.16 b), its observed speed will be almost equal to half the speed of light.

3.5 . Relationship between observed and true distance traveled

Let us consider how the observed and the true path traveled by a point are interconnected when it moves towards the observer or away from him.

Let the point move towards the observer.

Denote by τ some time interval that has passed by the observer's clock. Let, for example, $\tau = t_4 - t_2$ as shown in Fig. 3.6. It is obvious that the true path traveled s_{tr} (that is, the movement of the true location of the material point M_{tr}) for the time interval τ is equal to

$$s_{tr} = v_{tr}\tau,$$

and the observed path traveled s_{obs} (that is, the movement of the observed location of the material point M_{obs}) for the same time interval τ is equal to

$$s_{obs} = v_{obs}\tau.$$

It follows that the observed distance traveled s_{obs} and the true distance traveled s_{tr} are related to each other in the same proportion as the observed speed v_{obs} and true speed v_{tr} :

$$\frac{s_{obs}}{s_{tr}} = \frac{v_{obs}}{v_{tr}}. \quad (3.18)$$

From (3.18), taking into account (3.16a), one can obtain:

$$s_{obs} = \frac{s_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.19a)$$

Thus, the observed path traveled s_{obs} when a material point approaches the observer is directly proportional to the true path traveled s_{tr} . For the example shown in Fig. 3.6, the observed path traveled s_{obs} is more than the true path traveled s_{tr} for the time interval $\tau = t_4 - t_2$ by exactly 2 times.

Similarly, as the point moves away from the observer, the following relation holds:

$$s_{obs} = \frac{s_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.19b)$$

In general

$$s_{obs} = \frac{s_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.19c)$$

where the plus sign in the denominator is when the point is removed from the observer; minus sign - when it approaches the observer.

3. 6. Relationship between the observed and true length of a moving body

Let us find the dependence of the observed length of a moving body on its true length.

Consider a solid rod of length l_{tr} moving towards the observer (which is located at the origin O ISO) in the direction of its length, and exactly the same rod moving away from the observer (Fig. 3.8). The speed of the rods is equal to v_{tr} . On fig. 3.8 shows an example of the rod approaching the observer with a true speed v_{tr} equal to $0.5c$ and the rod moving away from the observer with a true speed equal to the speed of light.

Fig. 3.8. Movement of a solid rod: green indicates the true dimensions of the rod, blue indicates the observed

Let the observer be a radar that allows you to determine the distance to the near and far points of the rod.

In accordance with formula (3.11a), when the rod approaches the observer, the observed point of the rod closest to it will be at a distance

$$|b_{obs}| = \frac{|b_{tr}|}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}},$$

while the farthest observed point will be located at a distance from it

$$|a_{obs}| = \frac{|a_{tr}|}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}},$$

where $|b_{tr}|$ and $|a_{tr}|$ are the true distance from the observer to the near and far points of the rod, respectively;

b_{tr} and a_{tr} are coordinates on the X axis respectively, the near and far points of the rod.

In accordance with this, the observed length of the rod l_{obs} will be equal to

$$l_{obs} = |a_{obs}| - |b_{obs}| = \frac{|a_{tr}| - |b_{tr}|}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{l_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}},$$

that is, when the rod approaches the observer

$$l_{obs} = \frac{l_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.20a)$$

where l_{tr} is the true length of the rod.

When the rod moves away from the observer, its observed length is determined by a similar formula:

$$l_{obs} = |e_{obs}| - |d_{obs}| = \frac{|e_{tr}| - |d_{tr}|}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{l_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$$

$$l_{obs} = \frac{l_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.20b)$$

In general, the relationship between the observed l_{obs} and true length l_{tr} of the moving rod is determined by the relationship:

$$l_{obs} = \frac{l_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.20c)$$

where the "plus" sign in the denominator is placed when the rod moves away from the observer, "minus" - when approaching the observer.

Special cases. A meter ruler moving towards the observer in the direction of its length at a speed equal to half the speed of light will be observed as a two-meter ruler. At 0.999 s a meter ruler approaching an observer will be observed as a kilometer pole. When moving away at a speed close to the speed of light, a meter ruler will be observed as 50 cm.

In accordance with the results obtained, it can be seen that the observed length of a meter ruler moving in the direction of its length, when approaching the observer, is equal to:

$$l_{obs} = \mu_{np} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$$

and when moving away from the observer:

$$l_{obs} = \mu_{yd} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$$

In these expressions, μ_{np} and μ_{yd} are the coefficients of direct proportionality, according to which the observed length of the rod increases when it approaches the observer, or decreases when it moves away from the observer compared to the true length of this rod.

Fig. 3.9. Graph of the dependence of the observed length of a meter ruler on the true speed of movement. Positive velocity values correspond to the removal of the ruler from the observer (the ruler becomes shorter according to observations), negative values correspond to its approach to the observer (the ruler becomes longer)

Thus, the coefficients μ_{np} and μ_{yd} are numerically equal to the observed length of a meter ruler moving in the direction of its length towards or away from the observer.

On fig. 3.9 shows a graph of the dependence of the observed length of a meter ruler on the speed of movement. Positive velocity values correspond to the removal of the ruler from the observer, negative values correspond to its approach to the observer.

Dimensions of moving volumetric bodies

Let us consider the observed dimensions of volumetric solids moving towards or away from the observer located at the origin of the IFR.

Let, for example, a rigid body be a sphere with a diameter R (Fig. 3.10).

Similarly to the case with the motion of the rod considered above, one can obtain the longitudinal observed size of the ball (along the line of motion), which will be equal to the value

$$l_{obs} = \frac{l_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{2R}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$$

where $l_{tr} = 2R$ is the true size (diameter) of the ball;

the plus sign in the denominator takes place when the body moves away from the observer; minus sign - when the body approaches the observer.

A ball moving along the axis will be observed as a figure of rotation, resembling an ellipsoid of rotation with semi-axes

$$\left(\frac{R}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, R, R \right).$$

Fig. 3.10. motion of a solid ball. Green indicates the true size of the ball, blue - the observed.

Thus, the observed ball, when moving towards the observer, is extended along the line of motion. When moving away from the observer, the ball will be observed oblate, compressed along the line of motion. It is clear that these are only visible, observable changes in size. The true dimensions of the ball remain unchanged.

Note, however, that the observed change in the size of moving bodies is not an illusion. This is a real observable effect, these changes can theoretically be recorded by instruments and means of observation in the same way as instruments detect a change in the perceived frequency of sound vibrations when a sound source moves relative to a receiver.

In accordance with the obtained formulas, when the ball approaches the observer, when the true speed tends to the speed of light, the observed dimensions of the ball along the line of motion

will increase indefinitely (as well as its observed speed). So, for example, a ball with a diameter of 1 m, approaching at a speed of $0.99 c$, will be observed as an ellipsoid of revolution with a length (along the line of motion) of 100 m. That is, a ball approaching at such a speed will take on a long cigar-shaped shape.

A ball receding at the speed of light, on the contrary, will be observed spat out, at this speed a 1-meter diameter ball will be observed as an ellipse 50 cm thick.

3. 7. The relationship between the observed and the true rate of time of a moving clock

Consider such a quantity as the observed rate of time of the clock approaching the observer μ_{obs} . Let the clock be on a material point approaching the observer, and the observer monitors the readings of this clock using a video image transmitted to him via radio communication. In other words, let the readings of a clock located on a moving point be taken by a frame-by-frame video camera, from which the captured frames are transmitted to the observer using a radio data transmission channel. We assume that video frames are broadcast at a frequency of ν_{tr} .

By default, it is assumed that the time of a clock located on a moving material point coincides with the time of a clock that is stationary in the ISO, in the immediate vicinity of which the material point is moving at the time of their passage. In other words, if a material point at some point in time passes next to a clock that is stationary in the ISO, then the readings of the stationary clock and the clock of the moving point coincide.

The observed rate of time of the clock approaching the observer μ_{obs} is equal to the number of seconds that have elapsed according to the observed readings of these clocks in one second of a stationary clock located next to the observer. So, for example, if $\mu_{obs} = 2$, then this means that the second hand of the approaching clock observed on the video will move exactly 2 times faster than the second hand of the clock moves near the observer. In this case, the true rate of the clock time is equal to one: $\mu_{tr} = 1$.

Let synchronously with the transmitted frames of the captured video image, an observer located at the origin of the ISO coordinates also receive a radio wave with the same frequency ν_{tr} . In other words, one video frame is transmitted simultaneously with the beginning of the next transmitted radio wave.

Obviously, due to the fact that radio waves and captured video frames are transmitted to the observer synchronously with a frequency ν_{tr} , and also at the same speed of light c , then the radio waves and video frames received by the observer will also be observed synchronous, and the observed frequency of the received radio wave and the observed frequency received video frames will be determined by the expression

$$\nu_{obs} = \frac{\nu_{tr}}{1 - \frac{\nu_{tr}}{c}}$$

In accordance with this, the number of ν_{tr} video frames taken on a moving material point in one second will be reproduced by an observer in less than a second. At the same time, exactly ν_{obs} frames will be reproduced for the observer in one second, $\nu_{obs} > \nu_{tr}$.

If, for example, a video camera on an approaching point shoots a clock located on it, and the true speed of the point is equal to $\nu_{tr} = 0,5$ the speed of light, then the perceived frame rate ν_{obs} will be equal to $2 \nu_{tr}$. This means that in one second, according to the observer's clock, the readings of the approaching clock on the ideological image he observes will change by two seconds. The observed readings of a clock approaching the observer go faster than the stationary clock of the observer.

Obviously, there is a relation:

$$\frac{\mu_{obs}}{\mu_{tr}} = \frac{\nu_{obs}}{\nu_{tr}}$$

In other words, the ratio of the observed rate of time of the approaching clock μ_{obs} to the true rate μ_{tr} is equal to the ratio of the observed (receiver) frequency ν_{obs} to the true frequency of the transmitter ν_{tr} .

This follows from the synchronism of clocks and radio waves transmitted from the point of video frames, as well as from the synchronism of their reception by the observer.

From this we can conclude that the observed rate of time of the clock approaching the observer is equal to

$$\mu_{obs} = \frac{\mu_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.21a)$$

where μ_{tr} is the rate of time of a stationary clock, the value of which is equal to one.

Fig. 3.11 a). Transmitter oscillation frequency $\nu_{tr} = 5$ Hz: 5 waves are generated in 1 second by the clock moving towards the observer together with the transmitter

Fig. 3.11 b). Observed (perceived) oscillation frequency by the receiver $\nu_{obs} = 10$ Hz: 10 waves are received in 1 second by the clock of the receiver, which corresponds to 2 seconds by the clock of the transmitter. For 1 second, according to the clock of the receiver, 2 seconds pass (observed) according to the clock of the transmitter

The fact of the acceleration of the observed rate of the passage of time of the clock approaching the observer (simultaneously with the increase in the frequency of oscillations of the transmitter moving towards the observer perceived by the receiver) is illustrated in Fig. 3.11. On fig. 3.11a shows a 5 Hz wave generated by a moving transmitter. At this frequency, 5 waves are

generated in one second by a clock located next to the transmitter. On fig. 3.11, b shows the waves received (observed) by the receiver when the transmitter moves towards it at a speed of $0.5c$. At this speed, according to the formula of the Doppler effect, the observed frequency will be 10 Hz , which corresponds to two seconds of time according to the clock moving along with the transmitter. In other words, in one second according to the observer's clock, the observed time interval according to the clock approaching along with the transmitter will be equal to two seconds. The observed rate of time of the approaching clock μ_{obs} for this example will be equal to 2.

Similarly, it can be obtained that as the clock moves away from the observer

$$\mu_{obs} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.21b)$$

The generalized formula for the observed rate of time of a moving clock is:

$$\mu_{obs} = \frac{\mu_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{1}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.21c)$$

where the plus sign in the denominator is when the point is removed from the observer; minus sign - when it approaches the observer.

Consider the following example.

Let there be a clock on a moving material point. Consider a particular case of a point approaching an observer along a straight line connecting the point and the observer. Let flashes of light occur at this point with a frequency $\nu_{tr} = 1\text{ Hz}$, that is, with the frequency of changing the indications of the second hand of the clock (changes in the values of seconds on the digital clock dial) located at the point. Thus, the flashes will count the time of the clock at the point. Let, in addition, from a point, simultaneously with flashes, using radio signals of exact time, the indications of the clock located at the point are transmitted to the observer. We will assume that the clock at the point is synchronized with the ISO clock.

In accordance with the Doppler effect ν_{obs} , the frequency recorded by a fixed receiver of radio signals of exact time is determined by the expression:

$$\nu_{obs} = \frac{\nu_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}.$$

In this case, the observed clock readings at the point will lag behind the observer clock readings by a delay time Δt equal to the signal travel time from the point to the observer:

$$\Delta t = \frac{r_{obs}}{c} = \frac{r_{tr}}{c(1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c})} = \frac{r_{tr}}{c - v_{tr}},$$

where r_{obs} and r_{tr} are, respectively, the observed and true distances from the observer to the moving point.

Therefore, the time on the clock of the point, observed at the origin of the ISO, will be equal to:

$$t_{obs} = t_{tr} - \Delta t = t_{tr} - \frac{r_{tr}}{c - v_{tr}},$$

where t_{tr} is the current (true) time on the ISO clock, as well as on the point clock.

Thus, the true time of the clock of the point and the watch of the observer exactly coincide, but the observer receives information according to which the clock of the point is lagging behind. The lag time is always equal to the time of movement of a beam of light (an electromagnetic signal that carries information about time) from a point to an observer at the origin.

It should be noted that the observed rate of time at the approaching point will be equal to the value

$$\mu_{obs} = \nu_{obs} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{c}{c - v_{tr}} \text{ Hz}.$$

At the point approach speed $v_{tr} = 0,8 c$

$$\mu_{obs} = \nu_{obs} = \frac{1}{1-0,8} = 5\text{Hz.}$$

This means that the second hand of the clock of the point observed at the origin will move at a rate of 5 seconds (the observed time of the point) per 1 second according to the ISO clock. That is, the observer will see that the flow of time at the point has accelerated, as it were, 5 times. This is the perceived, observed flow of time at a point approaching the observer.

During the time when, for example, a second passes by the observer's clock, at $\Delta t = 30$ a point approaching at a speed of $0.8 c$ (according to his observations) it will pass (Fig. 3.12)

$$\Delta t_{np} = \frac{\Delta t}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{30}{0,2} = 150\text{sec.}$$

In accordance with this, if a terrestrial observer observes, using video communication, the astronauts of a spacecraft approaching at a speed $v_{tr} = 0,8 c$ for, say, 1 year, then the observer will see that the astronauts are moving 5 times faster, that the cosmonauts' speech rate is accelerated by 5 times, and that during the year of observation, the astronauts will become 5 years older. For 10 years of observing such an approaching spacecraft, an observer on Earth will see that the astronauts have aged 50 years (while his age has increased by only 10 years).

Since the observed time at the approaching point flows faster than the true time, then with the passage of time the lag of the observed time from the true time will decrease so that at the moment the point passes the origin, the observed time will be exactly equal to the true time.

At the receding point, flashes will be observed with a lower frequency than the frequency of seconds on the observer's clock, in accordance with the formula:

$$\nu_{obs} = \frac{\nu_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{c}{c + v_{tr}} \text{Hz.}$$

The observed rate of time at the receding point will be equal to the value

$$\mu_{obs} = \nu_{obs} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{c}{c + v_{tr}}.$$

At the same time, during the time when $\Delta t = 30$ seconds pass by the observer's clock, at a point moving away at the speed of light, according to his observations (Fig. 3.12)

$$\Delta t_{yA} = \frac{\Delta t}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} = \frac{30}{2} = 15\text{sec.}$$

According to his observations, at the receding point, time will flow slowly, although in fact, the clock at this point goes at the same pace as his. At the same time, according to the observed data, the clock at the point will lag more and more as the point moves away from the observer.

Fig. 3.12. The observed flow of time at a point approaching at a speed of $0.8 c$ and receding at the speed of light

If a terrestrial observer uses video communication to observe the astronauts of a spacecraft moving away from the Earth, the speed of which is equal to the speed of light, then he will see that the movements of the astronauts, as well as the speed of their speech, are slowed down by 2 times. In a year of observation, he will see that only half a year has passed on the ship, and in 10 Earth years, according to his observations, only 5 years will pass on the ship. For 30 years of earthly life, the observer will grow old by this age, while the astronauts will grow up only 15 years during this time.

The transformation coefficient $\mu_{obs} = \frac{1}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$ in (3.21) has the physical meaning of the observed rate of the clock at a point moving away from the observer or approaching the observer.

Conclusion . When the clock moves towards the observer, its observed rate of movement increases compared to the rate of movement of a stationary clock, and when the clock moves away from the observer, on the contrary, it decreases.

3. 8. The relationship between the observed and the true time interval, counted by a moving clock

Let us find the dependence of the observed time interval counted by the moving clock on the true time interval.

Let us consider a clock approaching an observer who observes its indications using a broadcast video image of the clock in real time. In accordance with (3.21a), if the true time interval passes by the approaching clock (and by the observer's clock) Δt_{tr} , then the time interval observed by the clock on the video image Δt_{obs} will be equal to

$$\Delta t_{obs} = \Delta t_{tr} \mu_{obs} = \frac{\Delta t_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.22a)$$

where μ_{obs} is the observed rate of time of the clock approaching the observer, equal to the number of seconds that have elapsed according to the observed readings of these clocks in one second of a stationary clock located near the observer .

When the clock moves away from the observer, in accordance with (3.21 b), the relation takes place:

$$\Delta t_{obs} = \frac{\Delta t_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.22b)$$

The generalized formula expressing the relationship between the observed and the true time interval, which is counted by a moving clock, obviously looks like this:

$$\Delta t_{obs} = \frac{\Delta t_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.22c)$$

In accordance with the formula (3.22a), *if a video report of astronauts* is broadcast to Earth from a video camera installed on a spacecraft that is approaching the Earth at a speed, then an observer on Earth will see an action accelerated by 2 times on the broadcast video image. $v_{tr} = 0,5 c$ The clock hands of the spacecraft in the video image will move 2 times faster than on Earth; all movements of astronauts in the video image will be accelerated by 2 times; all processes occurring on the ship will also be observed in 2 times accelerated; the astronauts' speech will also be 2 times faster.

If the spacecraft, from which the video report is being conducted, moves away at the same speed, then on the video image broadcast to Earth, the movements of the astronauts and their speech will be 1.5 times slower; the clock hands of the spacecraft will move 1.5 times slower than on Earth; all processes occurring on the ship will also go 1.5 times slower.

Clock movement on a closed route

Consider the movement of a clock, which is previously synchronized with the observer's fixed clock, along a closed path, first from the observer, then back to him.

At the moment the movement starts, the clock will be next to the observer, so it will show the observer exactly the same time as his stationary clock, which is always located next to him. As the moving clock moves away from the observer, its observed readings will go slower than the stationary clocks, and the difference between the readings of the moving clock and the stationary clock will increase as the distance to the moving clock increases. At any moment in time, the difference Δt between the readings of a moving clock and a stationary clock will be determined by the expression

$$\Delta t = \frac{r_{obs}}{c} = \frac{r_{tr}}{c(1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c})} = \frac{r_{tr}}{c - v_{tr}},$$

where r_{obs} and r_{tr} are the observed and true distances to the moving clock, respectively.

The value Δt represents the delay time for the receipt of information about the readings of the moving clock to the observer, equal to the time of the signal (light beam) movement from the clock to the observer.

As the clock moves back towards the observer, the distance to the clock will decrease; accordingly, the difference between the indications of a moving clock and a stationary clock will also decrease Δt

$$\Delta t = \frac{r_{obs}}{c} = \frac{r_{tr}}{c(1+\frac{v_{tr}}{c})} = \frac{r_{tr}}{c+v_{tr}}.$$

In this case, the observed readings of the moving clock will go faster, exactly compensating for their lagging behind the stationary clock, which occurred when the clock was removed.

After the clock returns to the observer, it will show exactly the same time as the clock that remained stationary.

In accordance with the Theory of Aberration, a twin brother who has returned from space travel will mature exactly as much as his homebody brother will mature. When twin brothers meet, their age will be exactly the same.

While the astronaut brother will be on a distant space journey, for example, at a distance of 10 light years from the Earth, his earthly brother will observe him on video reports from space with a signal arrival delay of 10 years (this is the time of light travel from spacecraft to Earth). Accordingly, on video reports, the brother-cosmonaut will look exactly 10 years younger than his true age, which is exactly equal to the age of the earthly brother. But as the ship returns from space travel and the distance to the ship decreases, the delay in receiving signals from the ship will decrease and at the moment the ship lands on Earth, this delay will become equal to zero. Accordingly, the age of the traveler brother will be exactly the same as the age of the homebody brother.

Thus, in accordance with the Theory of Aberration, a clock moving in the IFR relative to the observer goes exactly at the same speed as a stationary clock, and not faster or slower than them.

3. 9. The relationship between the observed and true frequency of a periodic process occurring on a moving point

Let us find the relationship between the observed and true frequency of a periodic process occurring on a moving point.

In accordance with (3.1), (3.21) and (3.22), if a certain periodic process occurs on a moving point, the frequency of which is equal to , f_{tr} then the observed (using a video image transmitted to the observer) frequency of this process will be equal to

as the point approaches the observer

$$f_{obs} = \frac{f_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.23a)$$

when the point moves away from the observer

$$f_{obs} = \frac{f_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.23b)$$

in general

$$f_{obs} = \frac{f_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.23c)$$

an electric motor with a rotor speed = 100 revolutions per minute operates f_{tr} on a spacecraft whose approach speed to the Earth is , $v_{tr} = 0,5 c$ then the rotor speed observed on the video image broadcast to Earth will be $f_{obs} = 200$ revolutions per minute, that is, it will be 2 times more than the true frequency.

If the ship moves away at the same speed, then on the video image broadcast from the ship, the observed rotor speed f_{obs} will be about 67 revolutions per minute (1.5 times less than the true frequency).

3.1 0. Generalization of the obtained results

It is surprising that relations (3.1), (3.2), (3.3), (3.4), (3.5), (3.6), (3.7), (3.8), (3.11), (3.16), (3.17), (3.19), (3.20), (3.21), (3.22) and (3.23), which connect the observed and true quantities of a moving body and the processes occurring on it, have the same form.

Table 3.1 provides a summary of the results obtained above.

Table 3.1 - Summary of the results

Value	Removal	Approximation
Radiation frequency (Doppler effect)	$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Angular speed of rotation of a point	$\omega_{obs} = \frac{\omega_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\omega_{obs} = \frac{\omega_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Circular (angular) point rotation frequency	$\omega'_{obs} = \frac{\omega'_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\omega'_{obs} = \frac{\omega'_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Point rotation frequency	$n_{obs} = \frac{n_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$n_{obs} = \frac{n_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Angular velocity of body rotation	$\omega^*_{obs} = \frac{\omega^*_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\omega^*_{obs} = \frac{\omega^*_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Circular (angular) body rotation frequency	$\omega^{*'}_{obs} = \frac{\omega^{*'}_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\omega^{*'}_{obs} = \frac{\omega^{*'}_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
body rotation frequency	$n^*_{obs} = \frac{n^*_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$n^*_{obs} = \frac{n^*_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Circular frequency of rectilinear oscillations of a material point	$\omega''_{obs} = \frac{\omega''_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\omega''_{obs} = \frac{\omega''_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Frequency of rectilinear oscillations of a material point	$n''_{obs} = \frac{n''_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$n''_{obs} = \frac{n''_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Distance to point	$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
body length	$l_{obs} = \frac{l_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$l_{obs} = \frac{l_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Passed path	$s_{obs} = \frac{s_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$s_{obs} = \frac{s_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Speed	$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Batch Process Frequency	$f_{obs} = \frac{f_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$f_{obs} = \frac{f_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Clock rate	$\mu_{obs} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\mu_{obs} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$

Value	Removal	Approximation
Time interval	$\Delta t_{obs} = \frac{\Delta t_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\Delta t_{obs} = \frac{\Delta t_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$

Modern classical physics (at least judging by the physics courses taught in our time in higher educational institutions) many of the phenomena expressed by the relationships given in Table 3.1 are unknown.

In particular, one of the curious facts that is not described in physics textbooks is that if we measure with the help of electromagnetic waves (for example, using a radar or a laser range meter) the speed of a body moving towards the observer, then the measurements will show: the observed (measured) the speed of the body is greater than its true speed. At a true speed v_{tr} greater than 0.5 the speed of light, its observed speed v_{obs} will exceed the speed of light: a speed-measuring radar or laser rangefinder will record FTL!

In this case, there is no upper limit (limit) for the observed (measured) speed; it tends to infinity as the true speed approaches the speed of light. This can be seen from the formula (3.16a): at the $v_{tr} \rightarrow$ observed speed $v_{obs} \rightarrow \infty$.

Modern physics does not use the concepts of the observed and true location of a material point, the observed and true distances to the point, the speed of its movement, the length of the body, the rate of the clock, the time interval, the frequency of periodic processes. Nevertheless, the introduction of these concepts seems useful and even necessary to describe the motion of bodies and the processes occurring on them at speeds comparable to the speed of light.

Table 3.2 shows the relationship between the concepts that are used in the expressions of table 3.1.

Table 3.2 shows that the *observed quantities* presented in the columns of the table Q_{obs} correlate with the corresponding *true quantities* Q_{tr} in the same way as the observed (perceived by the receiver) frequency of the radiation correlates with the true frequency of the radiation source in the Doppler effect. The same type of formulas presented in Table 3.1 gives reason to assume that the physical nature of the phenomena described by these formulas is, in fact, the same.

Relations between concepts

Table 3.2 - Relations between concepts

Value	observed value, Q_{obs}	True value, Q_{tr}
Radiation frequency (Doppler effect)	Observed (perceived by the receiver) frequency, ν_{obs}	The true frequency of the radiation source, ν_{tr}
Angular velocity	Observed angular velocity, ω_{obs}	true angular velocity, ω_{tr}
Circular frequency	Observed circular frequency, ω'_{obs}	true circular frequency, ω'_{tr}

Value	observed value, Q_{obs}	True value, Q_{tr}
Frequency of rotation or oscillation	Observed frequency of rotation or oscillation, n_{obs}	True frequency of rotation or oscillation, n_{tr}
Distance to point	The observed distance to the point, r_{obs}	True distance to point r_{tr}
body length	Observed body length, l_{obs}	true length body, l_{tr}
Passed path	Observed distance travelled, s_{obs}	True path traveled s_{tr}
Speed	observed speed, v_{obs}	True speed, v_{tr}
Batch frequency	The observed frequency of a batch process, f_{obs}	The true frequency of the batch process, f_{tr}
Clock rate	Observed clock rate, μ_{obs}	The true pace of the clock, $\mu_{tr} = 1$
Time interval	Observed time interval, Δt_{obs}	True time interval Δt_{tr}

The same type of relationships presented in Table 3.1 allows us to formulate a new, previously unknown, physical law, which we called the law of aberration (Latin *aberratio* - deviation, removal) of the physical quantities of the body. The use of the term “aberration” is due to the fact that the observed quantities of a body change in comparison with the true quantities of the body as it moves relative to the observer. The reason for this deviation is caused by the movement of the material body relative to the observer, as well as the delay in the receipt of information about the body by the observer due to the finite speed of information propagation (the speed of light). At an infinitely high speed of light, the observed quantities of the body would be equal to the true ones.

When the speed of movement of the body is much lower than the speed of light, that is, at $v_{tr} \ll c$, the observed quantities are almost equal to the true quantities, that is $Q_{obs} \approx Q_{tr}$. This follows from the relationship between observed and true quantities.

3.1 1. The law of aberration of physical quantities

We formulate the law of aberration of physical quantities as follows.

The true dimensions of a body during its movement remain constant and do not depend on speed. The observed quantities of a body moving along the line connecting it and the observer are directly proportional to the same true quantities and, with uniform motion, are inversely proportional to the coefficient

$$k = 1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c},$$

where v_{tr} and c are, respectively, the true speed of the body and the speed of light;

the “plus” sign – when the body moves away from the observer, the “minus” sign – when the body approaches him.

The list of body values that obey this law: the distance from the observer to the body; the path traveled by the body; body length; the speed of the body; the pace of the passage of time located on the body of the clock; time interval counted by the clock located on the body; the frequency of the radiation source located on the body; angular velocity, circular (angular) frequency and frequency of rotation of a material point along a circle; angular velocity, circular (angular) frequency and frequency of rotation of the body around the axis; circular frequency and frequency of oscillations of rectilinear harmonic oscillations of a material point, as well as the frequency of a periodic process occurring on the body. Currently, this law includes 16 quantities.

In mathematical form, the law of aberration has the form:

$$Q_{tr} = const.$$

As the point approaches the observer

$$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.24a)$$

when the point moves away from the observer

$$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.24b)$$

in general

$$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.24c)$$

where Q_{obs} and Q_{tr} are the observed and true quantities of the body, respectively;

v_{tr} and c are, respectively, the true speed of the body and the speed of light;

the plus sign - when the body moves away from the observer, the minus sign - when the body approaches him.

The inverse (3.24) relations are expressed as follows:

as the point approaches the observer

$$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.25a)$$

when the point moves away from the observer

$$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.25b)$$

in general

$$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.25c)$$

where v_{obs} is the observed velocity of the body;

the minus sign - when the body moves away from the observer, the "plus" sign - when the body approaches it (the signs in the denominator of expressions (3.25) are inverted, that is, they are set "oppositely" compared to the signs in the denominator of expressions (3.24)).

The observed speed of the body is defined as a special case (3.24):

as the point approaches the observer

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.26a)$$

when the point moves away from the observer

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.26b)$$

in general

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (3.26c)$$

The true speed of the body is calculated as a special case (3.25):

as the point approaches the observer

$$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}. \quad (3.27a)$$

when the point moves away from the observer

$$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}. \quad (3.27b)$$

in general

$$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}. \quad (3.27c)$$

where the minus sign is when the body moves away from the observer, the plus sign is when the body approaches it (the signs in the denominator of expressions (3.27) are inverted, that is, they are set "oppositely" compared to the signs in the denominator of expressions (3.26)).

The second form of writing the law of aberration of physical quantities

Let us denote v_{tr}^c the ratio of the true speed of the body v_{tr} to the speed of light:

$$v_{tr}^c = \frac{v_{tr}}{c}.$$

The value v_{tr}^c has the physical meaning of the true speed of the body v_{tr} , expressed in the speed of light (in fractions of the speed of light). At true speed v_{tr} , equal to the speed of light, the value v_{tr}^c is equal to one.

We will call the quantity v_{tr}^c *the number of the true speed* of the body (by analogy with the Mach number), which is the ratio of the speed of the flow of a liquid or gas to the speed of sound at a given point in the flow.

The corresponding value v_{obs}^c equal to the ratio of the observed speed of movement of a body v_{obs} to the speed of light,

$$v_{obs}^c = \frac{v_{obs}}{c},$$

will be called *the number of the observed velocity* of the body.

The relations between the quantities v_{tr}^c and v_{obs}^c have the form:

$$v_{obs}^c = \frac{v_{tr}^c}{1 \pm v_{tr}^c}, \quad (3.28)$$

where the “plus” sign is when the body moves away from the observer, the “minus” sign – when the body approaches him;

$$v_{tr}^c = \frac{v_{obs}^c}{1 \mp v_{obs}^c}, \quad (3.29)$$

where the “minus” sign is when the body moves away from the observer, the “plus” sign when the body approaches him.

The signs in relations (3.29) are inverted (put in reverse) compared to the signs in relations (3.28).

Taking this into account, the law of aberration of physical quantities of a body moving relative to the observer can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{tr} &= const. \\ Q_{obs} &= \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 \pm v_{tr}^c}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.30)$$

where the plus sign is when the body moves away from the observer, the minus sign when the body approaches him.

The inverse expression (3.30) can be written as

$$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 \mp v_{obs}^c}, \quad (3.31)$$

where the minus sign is when the body moves away from the observer, the plus sign is when the body approaches it. The signs in relations (3.31) are inverted (set the other way around) compared to the signs in relations (3.30).

The third form of writing the law of aberration of physical quantities

If we denote the first derivative of the true distance from the observer to the body r_{tr} with respect to time

$$\dot{r}_{tr} = \frac{dr_{tr}}{dt},$$

then the law of aberration of physical quantities can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{tr} &= const. \\ Q_{obs} &= \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 + \frac{\dot{r}_{tr}}{c}}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.32)$$

The quantity $\dot{r}_{tr}$ represents the rate of change of the true distance from the observer to the body r_{tr} . This speed is positive when the body moves away from the observer, and negative when the body approaches him.

The inverse expression of the true quantities in terms of the observed quantities has the form

$$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 - \frac{\dot{r}_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.33)$$

where $\dot{r}_{obs}$ is the rate of change in the observed distance from the observer to the body r_{obs} (the first derivative with respect to time):

$$\dot{r}_{obs} = \frac{dr_{obs}}{dt}.$$

Note that the true and observed velocities $\dot{r}_{tr}$ differ from each other in these ratios as well. $\dot{r}_{obs}$ They can take both positive (when the body moves away from the observer) and negative (when the body approaches the observer) values.

Novelty

The novelty of the presented physical law is as follows.

According to modern physical concepts, when observing a moving body using acoustic, light or radio signals, one can obtain incorrect ideas about the position of the moving body, its shape and speed, as well as the running of the clock on this object [10].

The phenomenon of these distortions occurs due to the delay of light signals coming to the observer from the object.

Some of the formulas of the law of aberration given in Table 3.1 were obtained earlier in previous studies [Ibid.].

In this paper, for the first time, the concepts of true and observed quantities of a body and the processes occurring on it are formulated.

It is shown that the true quantities are not available for measurement by an observer remote from the moving body. Only observable quantities are available to him for measurement, using which the true quantities can be determined by the method of indirect measurements.

For the first time, the law of aberration of the values of a moving body was formulated, which relates the observed and true quantities. In mathematical form, the law of aberration is expressed by relations (3.24).

For the first time, general expressions (3.25) are obtained for converting observed quantities into true ones.

Experimental confirmation of the formulas for the law of aberration of body values is an important element of novelty.

Thus, a new, previously unknown law of aberration of the physical quantities of a body as it moves relative to an observer has been discovered, which in itself is a significant event for world and even more so for Russian science. Since 1991, not a single discovery of a previously unknown physical law has been registered in the recent history of the Russian Federation.

3.1 2. On the physical law

In physics, a law refers to stable connections between quantities, repeated in many experiments, inherent in the very nature of phenomena [11 , p. 14]. Physical laws are objective, i.e. act against the will or desire of people.

Richard Feynman, in his book “The Nature of Physical Laws” writes: “There is a rhythm and pattern between natural phenomena ... we will call these rhythms and patterns physical laws” [12].

The laws of physics describe phenomena observed in nature. So, for example, Kepler's three laws completely describe the motion of the planets around the Sun.

Speaking about the laws of physics, we can distinguish the following inherent features and features [11-14].

1. A physical law expresses a regularity (connection) between natural phenomena, formulated, as a rule, in *mathematical form* .
2. A physical law expresses *the relationship* between physical quantities that can be measured.
3. Physical laws tend to be *simple* in form.
4. Many physical laws, such as the law of gravity, are *universal* . The law of gravitation, for example, describes the phenomenon of attraction of both two balls and planets, as well as galaxies and clusters of galaxies.
5. Physical laws are usually *beautiful* . “A physical law must have mathematical beauty,” said Nobel laureate Paul Dirac.
6. Physical laws must be *confirmed experimentally* .
7. On the basis of physical laws, as a rule, various *inventions are created* .

The laws expressed in mathematical form describe the quantitative relationship between the physical quantities included in the law.

In physics, a physical quantity is a characteristic that reflects one of the important aspects of an object or phenomenon [11, p. 16]. A feature of a physical quantity is that it is *measured* , that is, compared with a quantity conventionally accepted as a unit of measurement.

The law of aberration (deviation) of physical quantities of a moving body

An important side of the set of seemingly heterogeneous phenomena is *the general regularity* (3.24) and (3.25), which consists in the fact that the observed (measured) heterogeneous (for example, time, distance and frequency are quantities of different kinds) values of the body when it moves relative to observers *behave in the same way* , that is, *they change quantitatively in the same way* when the speed of the body changes. In other words, a whole range of observable quantities with a change in the state of motion changes according to the same law:

$$Q_{obs} = \mu \times Q_{tr},$$

where Q_{obs} and Q_{tr} are the observed and true quantities of the body, respectively;

μ - coefficient of proportionality, the value of which depends on the speed of the body relative to the observer,

$$\mu = \frac{1}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}},$$

v_{tr} - the true speed of the body;

sign plus sign - when the body moves away from the observer, minus sign - when the body approaches him .

This general pattern is expressed by the presented law of aberration (change) of the physical quantities of a moving body.

This law connects different observed (measured) values of a moving body with the same true quantities.

Since completely heterogeneous quantities turned out to be related by the same law in form, we can say that the presented law of aberration of quantities is a general physical law.

One of the important universal aspects that unite many dissimilar phenomena is that when measuring the magnitudes of a distant body moving relative to the observer at a speed comparable to the speed of light, the observer in all cases will measure (fix) the observed value, which differs from the *true* value Q_{obs} . In this case, one could speak of an error (distortion) of measurements, but given the general pattern and general nature of such “errors”, the term “aberration ” *is used within the framework of the Theory of Aberration* , which means *a change in physical quantities*.

The coefficient of proportionality μ between many observed Q_{obs} and true Q_{tr} values turned out to be, on the one hand, simple (as befits the coefficient of a physical law), and on the other hand, the same for 16 values.

Remarkable is the fact that many heterogeneous measured quantities of a body change according to the same law with a change in the speed of movement.

With an increase in the speed of movement relative to the observer, a large number of observed quantities of the body and the processes occurring on it will increase (when moving towards the observer) or decrease (when moving away from the observer) in the same way, with the same coefficient of proportionality μ . This fact is reflected for the first time in the Theory of Aberration by the law of aberration of physical quantities.

Below is the amazing beauty of the law of aberration of quantities. For physicists, beauty is symmetry and harmony. The relationships of the law of aberration are in many respects wonderfully symmetrical, and therefore wonderfully beautiful.

The law of aberration (3.24) has all the features of a physical law

The law of aberration of physical quantities of a moving body has all the features (signs) of a physical law listed above.

1. The law of aberration in mathematical form expresses the general relationship between the state of motion of a body and a number of observable (measured) heterogeneous physical quantities of this body.
2. The law of aberration expresses the relationships between physical quantities that can be measured.
3. The law of aberration is simple in form.
4. The law of aberration is universal. Observable bodies and the processes occurring on them, as well as planets, luminaries, galaxies and clusters of galaxies, are subject to the law of aberration.
5. The law of aberration is amazingly beautiful.
6. The law of aberration has been confirmed experimentally.
7. Inventions have been made using the law of aberration.

Therefore, the established connection between a set of quantities, expressed by mathematical formulas (3.24) and (3.25), can reasonably be called a physical law.

3.1 3. Applicability of the law of aberration

The law of aberration of the values of a body moving relative to the observer is applicable for the true speeds of motion v_{tr} of a material point in the range from zero to the speed of light.

3.1 4. Measurement of body values by a remote observer

If the measurement of the values of a moving body is carried out by a remote observer, and the measurement is carried out using electromagnetic waves (for example, using a radar), then it must be borne in mind that only observable quantities are available for direct measurement. An example is the Doppler effect. The observer (receiver) can only measure the perceived frequency of the radiation. The radiation frequency of the source itself is not available for direct measurement by a remote observer. It can be measured only by the direct measurement method, in which the desired value of the radiation frequency is determined on the basis of the results of direct measurements of the frequency perceived by the receiver, which is functionally related to the desired value.

Thus, the true quantities Q_{tr} can be measured by the method of indirect measurement, according to which the observed quantities are first measured (by the method of direct measurement) Q_{obs} , then, using the functional relationship (3.25), the true quantities are determined Q_{tr} .

Consider an example of measuring the distance to a moving material point using a radar. Radar can only determine the observed distance to a point r_{obs} .

The true distance to a point can be measured by first measuring the observed distance to the point r_{obs} , then calculating the true distance r_{tr} using the functional relationship between r_{obs} and r_{tr} :

$$r_{tr} = \frac{r_{obs}}{1 \mp \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.30)$$

where the minus sign is when the body moves away from the observer, the plus sign is when the body approaches it.

Expression (3.30) is a special case of formula (3.25 c).

The observed speed v_{obs} , which is used in this formula, can be determined using two or more measurements of the observed distance r_{obs} :

$$v_{obs} = \frac{|r_{obs}(t_2) - r_{obs}(t_1)|}{t_2 - t_1}, \quad (3.29)$$

where $r_{obs}(t_1)$ and $r_{obs}(t_2)$ are the distances to the point measured by the radar at the times t_1 and t_2 respectively.

Thus, the algorithm for measuring the true distance r_{tr} to a material point moving relative to the observer looks like this:

1. Using a means of measuring the distance to a material point, two or more measurements of the observed distance are made r_{obs} .
2. Based on the measured values r_{obs} , using formula (3.29), the observed velocity of the material point is determined v_{obs} .
3. Using formula (3.30), v_{obs} the true distance to the moving material point is calculated from the observed speed r_{tr} and the observed distance r_{obs} .

So, only the observed quantities of a moving body are available for direct measurement by a remote observer Q_{obs} . The true magnitudes of a moving body Q_{tr} are not available for direct measurement. They can be determined by indirect measurement with and using relations (3.25).

3.15. Graph of changes in observed quantities depending on the speed

On fig. 3.13 shows a graph of changes in the observed (measured) physical quantities of the law of aberration of a body moving relative to the observer, depending on the speed.

Fig . 3.13 . Graph of changes in the observed physical quantities of a moving body, depending on the speed , expressed in fractions of the speed of light. Positive values of velocities correspond to the removal of the body from the observer, negative values correspond to its approach to the observer.

The graph shows the values of the observed (measured) physical quantities at different speeds of the body if the true value of the physical quantity is equal to one.

So, for example, when the speed of the body approaching the observer is equal to 0.5 of the speed of light, all the physical quantities included in the law of aberration, when measured, will increase twice as compared to the same true quantities (at a speed equal to zero).

3.1 6. Mathematical beauty of the law of aberration of physical quantities

Based on the principles of aberration of the location and aberration of the physical quantities of a moving body, this section made the discovery of a previously unknown physical law of aberration of physical quantities and processes occurring on it, according to which the observed quantities of a body moving along a line connecting it and the observer are directly proportional to the same true quantities. In mathematical form, the law of aberration can be written in the following form

$$Q_{obs} = \mu \times Q_{tr}, \quad (3.30)$$

where Q_{obs} and Q_{tr} are the observed and true quantities of the body, respectively;

μ - coefficient of proportionality, determined by the formula as the point approaches the observer

$$\mu = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.31a)$$

when the point moves away from the observer

$$\mu = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.31b)$$

in general

$$\mu = \frac{1}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (3.31c)$$

where v_{tr} is the true speed of the body;

the plus sign - when the body moves away from the observer, the minus sign - when the body approaches him.

The inverse relationship between true and observed quantities is expressed as follows:

$$Q_{tr} = \mu' \times Q_{obs}. \quad (3.32)$$

In this expression, the coefficient μ' is determined by the formula as the point approaches the observer

$$\mu' = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.33a)$$

when the point moves away from the observer

$$\mu' = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.33b)$$

in general

$$\mu' = \frac{1}{1 \mp \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}, \quad (3.33c)$$

where v_{obs} is the observed speed of movement of the body;

the “minus” sign - when the body moves away from the observer, the “plus” - when the body approaches him (the signs in the denominator of expressions (3.33) are inverted, that is, they are placed “opposite” compared to the signs in the denominator of expressions (3.31)).

It is important to note that in formulas (3.31) the value of *the true* speed appears v_{tr} , while in formulas (3.33) *the observed* speed of movement is used v_{obs} .

Besides,

$$\mu = \frac{1}{\mu'} \quad (3.34a)$$

and correspondingly

$$\mu' = \frac{1}{\mu}. \quad (3.34b)$$

The observed and true speeds of movement are related by the relations

as the point approaches the observer

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.35a)$$

$$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}} \quad (3.35b)$$

when the point moves away from the observer

$$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \quad (3.36a)$$

$$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}} \quad (3.36b)$$

It can be seen that expressions (3.30) - (3.36) have an amazing mathematical beauty: they are many-sidedly symmetric.

Symmetry is expressed in the fact that the formulas connecting the observed and true quantities, when approaching and receding, are transformed from one to the other by a replacement, on the one hand; the plus sign to the minus sign and vice versa, and on the other hand, by replacing the true speed with the observed one and vice versa (Table 3.4). With such a replacement, the formulas of the law of aberration retain a similar form. The polyhedral symmetry of the ratios of the law of aberration is shown by arrows in Table. 3.4-3.7.

Table 3.4 - Polyhedral symmetry of the ratios of the law of aberration

Direction of travel	Observed quantities, Q_{obs}	True quantities, Q_{tr}
body approach	$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$
body removal	$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$

Table 3.5 - Polyhedral symmetry of the relationship between the observed and true speed

Direction of travel	observed speed, v_{obs}	True speed, v_{tr}
body approach	$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$
body removal	$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$

Table 3.6 - Symmetry of relationships between proportionality coefficients connecting observed and true quantities

	Observed quantities, Q_{obs}	True quantities, Q_{tr}
Relationships between quantities	$Q_{obs} = \mu \times Q_{tr}$	$Q_{tr} = \mu' \times Q_{obs}$
Direct and inverse proportionality factors	$\mu = \frac{1}{\mu'}$	$\mu' = \frac{1}{\mu}$

Table 3.7 – Polyhedral symmetry of relations connecting the coefficients of proportionality of the law of aberration with the observed and true speed

Direction of travel	μ	μ'
body approach	$\mu = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\mu' = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$
body removal	$\mu = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\mu' = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$

In tables 3.4-3.7, the arrows reflect the multifaceted *mathematical* symmetry of the ratios of the law of aberration of the physical quantities of the body as it moves relative to the observer.

Mathematical symmetry expresses the beauty of the law of aberration of physical quantities, which physical laws must have.

We will return to the question of the physical content of the beauty of the law of aberration below.

3. 17. Discussion of results

The discovery of the laws of nature is a rather rare event. Over the entire history of mankind, about a hundred different physical laws have been discovered, and only some of them are formulated using formulas. Thus, in textbooks and reference books on physics there are about 70-100 different laws of physics, see, for example, [8, 15]. In the textbook on physics by Yu. A. Seleznev, it is noted that out of 35 laws of elementary physics, only 17 are formulated using mathematical equations [16].

In this work, we had a unique opportunity to formulate a previously unknown law of aberration of physical quantities in mathematical form (3.24), (3.25).

Table 3.1 shows 16 physical quantities of the body and the processes occurring on it, which obey the law of aberration. However, it is not excluded that the list of these quantities can be expanded.

The previously unknown law of aberration presented in this work belongs to such a branch of physics as mechanics.

4. The Amazing Beauty of the Law of Aberration

Beauty is a very good criterion for choosing the right theory. *Gell -Mann, Nobel laureate*

4.1. On the beauty of physical law

The Concise Oxford Dictionary defines symmetry as “beauty due to the proportionality of the parts of the body or any whole, balance, likeness, harmony, consistency” [17]. The law of aberration is a simple and surprisingly beautiful law. Its beauty is expressed in the harmony, proportionality and symmetry of the resulting transformations and relationships between the true and observed worlds.

Nobel laureates in physics say the following about the beauty of physical laws.

“We believe that nature is best described by equations that are as simple, beautiful, compact and universal as possible ¹,” said Leon Max Lederman , who received the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1988 for his discovery of the muon neutrino.

“Of course, when we read about new theories and see how beautiful and simple they are, they have a considerable advantage. We believe that such theories have a much greater chance of being successful,” said Gerard Hooft , winner of the 1999 Nobel Prize in Physics.

“Physical laws must have mathematical beauty ²,” said Paul Dirac, winner of the Nobel Prize in Physics for 1933.

“Having tasted beauty in the heart of the world, we yearn for more. In this quest, I think there is no more promising guide than beauty itself ³,” said Frank Wilczek, winner of the 2004 Nobel Prize in Physics for his discovery of asymptotic freedom in the theory of strong interactions.

And finally, we note the remarkable statement about the beauty of the theoretical physicist Gell -Mann, Nobel Prize in Physics in 1969 for discoveries related to the classification of elementary particles and their interactions. He said: "In fundamental physics, a beautiful or elegant theory is more likely to be correct than an inelegant theory."

The beauty of physical and mathematical theory is expressed by symmetry, proportionality of parts, their similarity and harmony. The law of aberration is amazingly beautiful. The formulas for the transformations of the true and observed physical quantities of a moving body in the law of aberration turned out to be surprisingly harmonious and symmetrical.

¹Quoted in: Hossenfelder S. The Ugly Universe: How the Search for Beauty Baffles Physicists.

²Quoted from: Stuart I. Truth and Beauty: A World History of Symmetry. Moscow: Corpus, 2010.

³Wilchek F. The beauty of physics: comprehending the structure of nature. M.: ANF , 2016.

4.2. Two worlds: the true world and the perceived (observed) world

The law of aberration is the law of two worlds: the perceived (observed) world that we see and can observe with the help of any physical instruments (for example, telescopes, if we are talking about space objects), and the true (real) world. When speaking of the "true" world, the word "true" should be put in quotation marks, since for each individual observer the "true world" is the supposed world. The true world is, in a sense, the world of the future. Let's explain this.

Imagine that we are holding a pen at arm's length and looking at the tip of the pen. The observed location of the pen tip is at point *A* in our 3D space (Figure 4.1).

Fig. 4.1. The observed location and the true location of the pen tip differ from each other (not to scale)

However, the light needs some time (quite distinguishable for modern physical devices) in order to reach ("get") from the tip of the pen to our eyes. Therefore, in fact, we do not see the pen itself, but its "historical" image, its history (even if it is only about 2 nanoseconds removed from us, 1 nanosecond is 10^{-9} seconds). If we move the handle to the right, then during this time the handle will move to point *B*, which is located elsewhere in space. The distance between points *A* and *B* is negligible. At a pen speed of 1 m/s, this distance is on the order of 2 nanometers (for comparison, many viruses are between 20 and 300 nanometers in size). It is important to understand that points *A* and *B* are points of different worlds. Point *A* is the point of the visible, perceived, observable world. Point *B* is the point of the "true" world that we cannot see. Information about the location of this point has not yet reached our eyes, and therefore point *B* for us is the relative future, which will become the present when the light from point *B* reaches us.

At low speeds and at short distances, the world we observe (point *A*) and the "true" world (point *B*) are so close to each other that they are practically indistinguishable from each other, they merge with each other.

But when we move on to consider the movement of physical bodies at speeds comparable to the speed of light, the observed and true world (in further presentation, when using the term “true world” we will omit the quotation marks) differ significantly from each other.

the GPS navigation satellite system, moving in orbit at an altitude of about 20 thousand 200 kilometers, has a linear speed of about 3.9 km / s. Accordingly, the true position of the satellite and its position observed from the ground may differ by 260 m or more (depending on the distance from the observer).

When the speed of an object approaching us is only 0.01 the speed of light (about 3 thousand km/s), the true distance and the observed distance to the object differ from each other by about 1%. In other words, already at this speed the observed and the true world are distinctly different worlds.

An even greater difference between the observed and the true worlds occurs when observing objects with cosmic velocities on a cosmic scale.

The true world is the world as we would see it if the speed of light were infinite. The observable world is the world as we observe it with our eyes and with the help of physical instruments.

The true physical dimensions of bodies are the dimensions of the bodies of the true world. Accordingly, the observed magnitudes of bodies are the magnitudes of the bodies of the observed world. The relationship between the observed and true quantities of bodies is expressed using the law of aberration of the physical quantities of a moving body.

4.3. Symmetry of the law of aberration

It is interesting to note that the true and observed worlds are mirror worlds, symmetrical to each other. The mathematically observable distance to a moving point and its speed depend on the true distance and speed, and this dependence is expressed by the relations of the law of aberration. Using the relations of this law, one can express the true distance and speed in terms of the observables.

For convenience of analysis, we summarize some relationships of the aberration law in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 - Polyhedral symmetry of transformations

	direct transformatio n _	Reverse transformatio n _	Proportionality of coefficients transformations
Deleting a point	$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$ $v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$r_{tr} = \frac{r_{obs}}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$ $v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$	$\mu_{y_d} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$ $\mu_{y_d} = \frac{1}{\mu'_{y_d}}$ $\mu'_{y_d} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$ $\mu'_{y_d} = \frac{1}{\mu_{y_d}}$
Point approximat ion	$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$ $v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$r_{tr} = \frac{r_{obs}}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$ $v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$	$\mu_{np} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$ $\mu_{np} = \frac{1}{\mu'_{np}}$ $\mu'_{np} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}}{c}}$ $\mu'_{np} = \frac{1}{\mu_{np}}$

It can be seen from the table that between the true and observed distances to a point and its velocities as it moves away and approaches, there is an amazing proportional and symmetrical relationship.

The formulas for converting true distances and velocities into observed ones and vice versa are symmetrical. 1

The formulas for the transformation of distances and velocities are symmetrical when approaching and when receding a point. 2

And, finally, there is a symmetry, 3 according to which the formulas for approximating a point in the observed world are similar to the formulas for removing a point in the real world and vice versa.

The right side of the table shows the coefficients for converting true distances (velocities) into observed ones μ_{y_d} , μ_{np} as well as observed distances (velocities) into true ones μ'_{y_d} , μ'_{np} when moving away and approaching a point. The coefficients μ_{y_d} and μ'_{y_d} are inversely proportional (like and μ_{np}) μ'_{np} . 4

a similar way (Table 2.1).

4.4. The physical meaning of the symmetry of transformations

Fig. 4.2. Zooming in and out of a point

The symmetry of transformations of motion parameters of a moving point is manifested in the following.

1. The symmetry of the motion parameters of the same v_{tr} point moving with speed as it approaches and moves away (Fig. 4.2).

Options	Approximation	Removal
Distance	$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$r_{obs} = \frac{r_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Speed	$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$v_{obs} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$

Symmetry is manifested in the similarity of formulas. Transformations for approximation and removal differ only in the sign in the denominator of the formula.

2. Symmetry of true and observed velocities when approaching and receding from the same point.

Options	Approximation	Removal
Observed speed	$v_{obs}^{np} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$v_{obs}^{yd} = \frac{v_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
True speed	$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}^{np}}{1 + \frac{v_{obs}^{np}}{c}}$	$v_{tr} = \frac{v_{obs}^{yd}}{1 - \frac{v_{obs}^{yd}}{c}}$

It can be seen from this table that tetrahedral symmetry takes place here.

On the one hand, the formulas for converting true to observed velocities and observed to true velocities are similar: in the top and bottom rows. In addition, the formulas in the left and right columns are also similar. The upper left and lower right formulas are also similar. The lower left and upper right formulas are similar.

3. Symmetry of transformation coefficients

Type of conversion	Approximation	Removal
Converting true parameters to observables	$\mu_{np} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$	$\mu_{y_d} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}$
Converting Observed Parameters to True Parameters	$\mu'_{np} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v'_{obs}}{c}}$	$\mu'_{y_d} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v'_{y_d}}{c}}$
Similarity and inverse proportionality	$\mu_{np} = \frac{1}{\mu'_{np}}$	$\mu_{y_d} = \frac{1}{\mu'_{y_d}}$
	$\mu'_{np} = \frac{1}{\mu_{np}}$	$\mu'_{y_d} = \frac{1}{\mu_{y_d}}$

As in the previous case, there is also four-sided symmetry here. Formulas are symmetrical
 - top and bottom;
 - left and right;
 - bottom left and top right;
 - upper left and lower right.

There is an inverse proportionality of the coefficients μ_{np} and μ'_{np} , as well as μ_{y_d} and μ'_{y_d} (see table).

Fig. 4.3. An amazing symmetry of the true and observed parameters of the movement of an approaching and receding point: a) the movement of bodies in one direction from the observer; b) the movement of bodies in different directions from the observer

In addition, the following similarity of the coefficients located along the diagonal takes place:

$$\frac{\mu_{y\Delta}}{\mu'_{np}} = \frac{\mu_{np}}{\mu'_{y\Delta}}$$

The multifaceted symmetry of the transformation coefficients, their similarity and proportionality determine the corresponding geometric symmetry of the true and observed worlds (true and observed coordinates of moving points in the IFR).

One can, for example, note the following symmetry of the true and observed parameters of the movement of an approaching and receding point (Fig. 4.3).

If $v_{tr}^{np} = v_{obs}^{y\Delta}$, then and $v_{obs}^{np} = v_{tr}^{y\Delta}$. If also at the same time $r_{tr}^{np} = r_{obs}^{y\Delta}$, then also takes place $r_{obs}^{np} = r_{tr}^{y\Delta}$.

Fig. 4.4. Polyhedral symmetry of the true and observed dimensions of the body as it approaches and recedes

On fig. 4.4 shows a body approaching the observer (above) and a body receding from it (below).

The figure shows:

l_{obs}^{np} and l_{tr}^{np} are, respectively, the observed and true lengths of the body approaching the observer ;

$l_{obs}^{y\Delta}$ and $l_{tr}^{y\Delta}$ are, respectively, the observed and true lengths of the body moving away from the observer .

The physical symmetry of the law of aberration of physical quantities is expressed in the fact that with the same true speed of approach of the body and the observed speed of removal of the body, that is, at , the $v_{tr}^{np} = v_{obs}^{y\Delta}$ true speed of removal of the body and the observed speed of approach of the body are also the same, that is $v_{tr}^{y\Delta} = v_{obs}^{np}$.

Moreover, in this case, with the same true length of the approaching body and the observed length of the receding body, that is, at , $l_{tr}^{np} = l_{obs}^{y\Delta}$ the true length of the receding body and the observed length of the approaching body are also the same, that is, $l_{tr}^{y\Delta} = l_{obs}^{np}$.

The true physical world and the observed physical world are many-sidedly symmetrical to each other.

This symmetry manifests itself not only in the mathematical formulas of the law of aberration of physical quantities, but also in the physical world itself, in the symmetry of various physical quantities.

The beauty of a physical theory is manifested, first of all, in the symmetry of transformations. The symmetry is beautiful (Figure 4.5).

Fig. 4.5. The beauty of symmetry

As we can see, polyhedral symmetry takes place in the law of aberration, in mirror transformations of true and observed physical quantities of a moving body.

We saw above that the law of aberration of quantities has mathematical beauty (symmetry), which manifests itself in the fact that the formulas connecting the observed and true quantities, when approaching and receding, are transformed from one to the other by replacement, on the one hand; the plus sign to the minus sign and vice versa, and on the other hand, by replacing the true speed with the observed one and vice versa (Table 4.2). With such a replacement, the formulas of the law of aberration retain a similar form. Double-sided arrows in the table. 4.2 display the mathematical symmetry of the formulas. Each of the four formulas presented in the table is similar to each. Obviously, behind the mathematical beauty of the formulas of the law of aberration lies physical symmetry, the beauty of nature, the real world.

Table 4.2 - Polyhedral symmetry of the ratios of the law of aberration

Direction of travel	Observed quantities	True quantities
body approach	$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 - v_{tr}^c}$	$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 + v_{obs}^c}$
body removal	$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 + v_{tr}^c}$	$Q_{tr} = \frac{Q_{obs}}{1 - v_{obs}^c}$

In graphical form, the polyhedral symmetry of the transformations of the true and observed quantities of a moving body is shown in fig. 4.6 . _ In the figure, the four "axes of symmetry" of the law of aberration are shown as red lines. Formulas that are symmetrical about each of the four axes are symmetrical. Each of the four formulas of the law of aberration shown in the figure is symmetrical to each!

Another kind of symmetry that takes place in the law of aberration is the symmetry of the observed and true quantities of the body between the past and the future.

If at the current moment of time a moving body passes in close proximity to the observer, then in the past this body approached the observer, and in the future it will move away from the observer.

Therefore, one more axis of symmetry can be depicted on the time axis. This axis passes through the "present", in which the body passes next to the observer (Figure 4.7).

In the past, this body approached the observer, so in the past there were formulas for the law of aberration of magnitudes for an approaching body. In the future, the body will move away from the observer, so in the future there will be formulas for the law of aberration of quantities for a moving body.

Fig. 4.6. The beauty of the law of aberration of physical quantities. The red lines represent the four "axes of symmetry" of the law of aberration. Formulas that are symmetrical about each of the four axes are symmetrical. Each of the four formulas of the law of aberration is symmetrical to each!

If at the current moment of time a moving body is approaching the observer, then going past, in the future it will move away from him. In this case, there will be a symmetry of the true and observed quantities with respect to the moment of time when the body passes by the observer.

If at the current moment of time the body is moving away from the observer, then in the past it approached him, and at some point in time passed by. There is also a symmetry between physical quantities in the past and in the future. The past and the future, between which there is symmetry, are separated by the moment the body passes by the observer.

Fig. 4.7. Symmetry of the observed and true quantities of the body between the past and the future

Thus, the law of aberration is amazingly beautiful. Beauty is expressed in the harmony and symmetry of the obtained transformations and ratios of the true and observed physical quantities of a moving body and the processes occurring on it. Beauty takes place both in the mathematical expressions of the law of aberration and in the physical world.

“Physicists have developed the concept of symmetry as an objective criterion for evaluating the structure of Nature. When there are two theories, physicists feel that the more symmetrical one is usually the more beautiful one. In the eyes of a physicist, *beauty implies symmetry* (highlighted by me. - A.P.)”⁴, - writes the famous theoretical physicist Anthony Zee .

The law of aberration is amazingly beautiful. The resulting transformations of the physical quantities of the body in the true and observed worlds are symmetrical. From them "breathes" harmony and beauty.

⁴Anthony Zee (2007) *Frightening Symmetry: The Search for Beauty in Modern Physics*, 2nd ed. Princeton University Press. ISBN 978-0-691-00946-9. 1986 1st ed. published by Macmillan .

4.5. conclusions

The law of aberration of the physical quantities of a body has a multifaceted mathematical and, accordingly, physical symmetry.

Mathematical symmetry is a reflection of the symmetry of the physical world, inherent in nature itself, the ongoing processes and phenomena of the objective reality surrounding us.

Mathematical symmetry is expressed in the fact that the relations of the law of aberration retain the same form when the plus sign is replaced by the minus sign and vice versa, as well as when the observed quantities are replaced by true ones and vice versa.

However, this simple "mechanical" replacement of mathematical symbols hides the physical symmetry and harmony of the universe.

The mathematical beauty of the formulas of the law of aberration is only a reflection of the inner physical beauty and harmony of the universe around us.

5. Popular science method of confirming the reliability of the law of aberration

One of the ways to check the reliability of the correlations of the law of aberration is to explain some correlations of the law of aberration “on the fingers”, extremely simply and accessible even to students of senior classes of general educational institutions so that the physical meaning of these correlations becomes extremely clear.

Let us give a popular science presentation of some correlations of the law of aberration in order to make sure of its reliability in the most understandable and simple way.

The popular science exposition of the law of aberration is useful in order to simply and convincingly convey to the reader some aspects of the law of aberration that seem difficult to him.

5.1. On the observed course of a moving clock

A child who catches up with his mother walking on the sidewalk understands that if you walk at the same speed as mother walks, you cannot catch up with her, and therefore you need to run faster than mother moves.

Any driver who drives along the highway catching up with another car knows that in order to catch up with it, you need to drive faster, at a higher speed than the other car is traveling (Fig. 5.1).

Fig. 5.1. To catch up with the car in front, you need to go faster than it.

A similar situation occurs with the course of the clock. And even a schoolboy understands: if his watch was one hour behind the exact time a week ago, and now they are not behind, then during the week this watch *went faster* than the exact clock (Fig. 5.2). In other words, in order for a lagging clock to catch up with an accurate clock, it must hurry up and go faster.

If the car behind us goes at the same speed as we do, it will never be able to catch up with our car.

If the lagging clock runs without speeding up, it will never be able to catch up with the correct clock.

Fig. 5.2. If some clocks lagged behind a week ago, and now they are not lagging behind, then this week they went *faster than* the exact clock and thus caught up with them

On the delay in the receipt of information about the readings of remote clocks and their lag

It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that when we examine some objects remote from us, we see the light that was reflected from them and went towards us for some time.

Looking at the stars, we see the light that came from these stars for millions of years. Therefore, looking at some star, we see its "historical image", we see it as it was millions of years ago. When we see the setting Sun on the horizon, we see light that was emitted by the Sun about 6 minutes ago. If there was a huge clock face on the surface of the Sun, and we could see their readings, then we would not see the current reading, but the reading that was about 6 minutes ago. In other words, if we looked at the clock in the Sun, we would see that it was 6 minutes *behind* (500 seconds to be exact).

If we could watch a watch with a huge dial on the Moon, we would similarly see that this watch shows the time that was about one second ago, because the light from the Moon travels to the Earth for about a second (more precisely 1.27 seconds). In other words, the observed readings of the lunar clocks would be 1.27 seconds behind our accurate clocks on Earth, assuming that the clocks on the Moon were synchronized with the accurate clocks on Earth.

Now let's imagine that we are watching the clock readings of a spacecraft located on the planet Neptune using video broadcasting. The light and radio signal from the planet Neptune travels to Earth for about four hours. And this means that the observed readings of the clock of this spacecraft will lag behind the earth clock by four hours! When our clock reads "12:00:00" (noon), the observed clock reading from the ship on Neptune, which we will see in the video image of the clock, will be "08:00:00" (four hours behind).

Suppose now that the ship from Neptune began to move towards the Earth. We will monitor the readings of the clock of this ship using a scoreboard that displays the video image of the clock transmitted from the ship.

Rendering on the display of the clock of a spacecraft that is approaching the Earth is always behind by the *delay time* required by the radio signal to convey information about the clock reading to the Earth. The delay time is obviously equal to the distance to the ship divided by the speed of

light (Figure 5.3). As the ship moves towards the Earth, the distance to it decreases, and at the same time, the lag of the ship's clock readings, which is equal to the delay time, *decreases* .

Fig. 5.3. The spacecraft clock on Earth *is lagging* by the delay time of the signal that carries the spacecraft clock to Earth

As the ship moves towards the Earth, the distance from the ship to the Earth decreases, which means that the delay in delivering clock readings to Earth also decreases; along with this, the lag of the ship's clock from the earth's clock decreases (Fig. 5.4). This means that the readings on the clock board of a ship moving towards the Earth *go faster* than the readings of the earth clock. In other words, the observed rate of time of the clock approaching the Earth in the process of movement is higher than the true rate of time of the earth clock (Fig. 5.5).

We will circle this very important conclusion in a box.

Clocks moving towards the observer, according to their observed indications, move faster than the observer's stationary clock

Fig. 5.4. As the ship approaches the Earth, the delay in the delivery of clock readings to the Earth decreases and, at the same time, the delay between the ship's clock and the earth clock decreases. When the lag of the readings of moving clocks decreases, they catch up with the Earth's clock, which means they go faster.

The reason for the acceleration of the observed readings of clocks moving towards the observer is the delay in the receipt by the observer of information about the readings of moving clocks and their movement. In each subsequent second, the clock moving towards the observer is *closer* than in the previous second. Therefore, the magnitude of the delay in the receipt of information about the readings of moving clocks by the observer *decreases as the movement progresses* (the readings of the moving clock lag behind the readings of the stationary clocks less and less), and this causes the effect of *accelerating* the course of the observed readings of the clock approaching the observer. Each next second, according to the observed indications of the clock approaching the observer, passes *faster than* the previous second *due to the decrease in delays* in the receipt of information about the time of these clocks.

The reason for the acceleration of the observed readings of clocks approaching the observer is the continuous decrease in the delay in the receipt of information by the observer about the readings of moving clocks as they move

Conclusion

If the clock used to be behind, but now it is accurate, it means that they *accelerated* their course in order to eliminate the lag.

The clock reading of a spacecraft that flies to the Earth *is behind* by the time of delivery of the signal about the clock reading of the ship to the Earth.

After landing on Earth, the ship's clock readings are accurate, so during the flight, the ship's clock *speeded* up to eliminate the lag.

The spacecraft clock was lagging due to a delay in the clock signal

Now the ship's clock is accurate

Fig. 5.5. If the clock readings on the spacecraft approaching the Earth lagged behind the earth clock due to a delay in the signal about the ship's clock readings, and now they do not lag behind, then when moving towards the Earth, the ship's clock readings went faster than the exact clock and therefore caught up *with* them

The case of spacecraft movement from the Earth

Let us consider the case of the spacecraft moving away from the Earth. As before, we will observe the readings of the ship's clock using a video image broadcast to Earth.

Obviously, if some clocks showed accurate time last week, but now they are behind, then this clock is running slower than accurate clocks (Fig. 5.6).

When the spacecraft is in flight at some distance from the Earth, the clock signal from the spacecraft will arrive at the earth with a delay (delay). The farther the ship moves away from the Earth, the greater will be the delay in the arrival of the signal with the clock readings, the more the readings of the ship's clock display on Earth will lag behind.

But if so, then this means that the display of the clock of the ship, which is moving away from the Earth, is slower than the exact clock (Fig. 5.7).

Fig. 5.6. If some clocks were accurate a week ago, but now they are lagging behind, then this week they were running *slower than* the exact clock.

Fig. 5.7. At the time of the launch of the spacecraft, the clock was accurate. As the spacecraft flies away from the Earth, due to the increasing signal delay, the spacecraft's clock display lags more and more. This means that the clock of the departing ship is running *slower than* the accurate clock.

Thus, when the clock moves away from the observer, the *observed* course of time of this clock is always slower than the motion of the observer's stationary clock. Clocks moving away from the observer, according to their observed readings, *run slower* than the observer's stationary clock.

Let's frame this conclusion.

Clocks moving away from the observer, according to their observed readings, run slower than the observer's stationary clock.

The reason for the slowdown in the observed readings of clocks moving away from the observer is the delay in the receipt by the observer of information about the readings of the moving clock and their movement. In each subsequent second, the clock moving from the observer is further away than in the previous second. Therefore, the magnitude of the delay in the receipt of information about the readings of moving clocks by the observer increases as the movement progresses (the readings of the moving clock lag behind the readings of the stationary clocks more and more), and this causes the effect of slowing down the progress of the observed readings of the clock moving away from the observer. Each next second, according to the observed indications of the clock moving away from the observer, passes *more slowly* (longer) than the previous second *due to the increase in delays* in the receipt of information about the time of these clocks.

The reason for the slowdown in the course of the observed readings of clocks moving away from the observer is the continuous increase in the delay in the receipt of information by the observer about the readings of moving clocks as they move.

Conclusions

So, when the clock moves towards the observer, the observed readings of the approaching clock go *faster* than the readings of the stationary clock, but when the clock moves away from the observer, the observed readings of the receding clock go *slower* than the readings of the observer's stationary clock.

The reason for this effect is the delay in the receipt of information about the observed indications to the observer, as well as in the movement of the clock relative to the observer.

Note that if the speed of light were infinitely high, then there would be no delay in the receipt of information about the course of the ship's clock, and no one would notice any deviation of the observed readings of the moving clock from the readings of the stationary clock.

It can be noted that the observed time of a moving clock is always equal to the difference between the true time and the delay time for the observer to receive information about the readings of the moving clock:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Observed Time} &= \text{Real Time} - \text{Delay Time} = \\ &= \text{Real Time} - \frac{\text{Observed distance}}{\text{Speed of light}} \end{aligned}$$

5. 2. Experiment to measure the observed rate of movement of a moving clock

The above conclusion that the clock moving towards the observer, according to their observed indications, goes faster than the clock located near the observer, was experimentally confirmed by a team of 100 scientists and engineers, including 8 doctors and 24 candidates of science, 20 graduate students. This experiment was carried out using a high-precision radar in 2022 in St. Petersburg.

The uniqueness of this experiment lies in the fact that the observed course of the moving clocks located on the aircraft was measured directly during the flight to and from the radar.

The scientific article "An experiment to measure the observed rate of a moving clock" was published in the scientific journal Automation and Software Engineering. 2022, No. 4(42) [18-20].

According to the "International Register of Achievements and Records", this work received the title of "Property of the Nation". The corresponding certificate "The largest scientific team of authors refuting the special theory of relativity" was received, which is awarded to the "scientific team for the experiment" [21].

5.3. Discussion of the results of the experiment of scientists from St. Petersburg and the conclusions of SRT

So, we see that the clock moving towards the observer, according to their observed indications, goes faster than the stationary clock. And this is understandable: if a week ago the observed readings of the clocks moving towards us lagged behind (due to the delay in the receipt of information about the clock), and today they do not lag behind (there is no delay), then the observed readings of these clocks in the process of movement went faster all week.

Previously, the clock lagged behind, but now it does not lag behind, which means that the clock accelerated the pace in order to compensate for the lag. Any student can easily understand this. If the hands of the clock used to be lagging behind, but now they are not lagging behind, then the clock hands somehow accelerated their movement in order to catch up with the exact time.

This is an obvious fact, which is confirmed by experiment.

The course of a clock moving towards us is similar to the movement of a car catching up with our car on the road (Fig. 5.8).

The car catching up with us lags behind us less and less, moving at a greater speed than we do.

Likewise, the clock approaching us lags our clock less and less, going faster than our clock.

The car catching up with us
lags behind us less and less

Our car

The clocks approaching us lag
behind our clocks less and less

Our watches

Clock progress

Fig. 5.8. The course of a clock moving towards us is similar to the movement of a car catching up with our car on the road.

5.4. Even schoolchildren understand the popular scientific presentation of the law of aberration

Fragments of the popular science presentation of the law of aberration presented in this work were given to students of general educational institutions who graduated from the 10th grade and moved to the 11th grade in order for them to evaluate the material for accessibility for understanding.

Four students out of four wrote in the reviews that this material was clear to them! This suggests that the meaning of the law of aberration is relatively simple, and it can be understood even by high school students of general education institutions, not to mention university students, and above all, technical universities.

6. Results and discussion

The paper presents a new, previously unknown law of aberration of physical quantities.

Graphic illustration of the law of aberration

A graphic illustration of the law of aberration is shown in fig. 6.1.

Fig. 6.1. The amazing beauty of the law of aberration of physical quantities. The law combines $2^4 = 16$ quantities

In fig. 6.1 the following notation is used:

v_{obs}^c and v_{tr}^c are, respectively, the observed and true velocities of the body, expressed in the speeds of light,

$$v_{obs}^c = \frac{v_{obs}}{c}, \quad v_{tr}^c = \frac{v_{tr}}{c}.$$

where v_{obs} and v_{tr} are the observed and true velocities of the body, respectively.

Summary of results

In table. 6.1 is a summary of some of the results of the law of aberration.

Table 6.1 - Summary of the results of the law of aberration

approaching the observer	Moving away from the observer
<i>Observed distance to a moving body</i>	
Approaching the Earth at a speed of 0.5 s (speed of light) the spacecraft will be observed 2 times farther than it actually is.	A spaceship receding from the Earth at the speed of light will be observed 2 times closer than it actually is.
<i>Moving body length</i>	
Approaching the Earth at a speed of 0.5 s, a spacecraft 100 meters long will be observed 200 meters long, 2 times longer than it actually is.	A 100 m long spacecraft receding from the Earth at the speed of light will be observed as 50 m long, 2 times shorter than it actually is.
<i>The observed speed of a moving body</i>	
With the true speed of the spacecraft approaching the Earth equal to 0.5 s its observed speed will be equal to the speed of light, that is, 2 times more than it actually is.	With the true speed of the spacecraft moving away from the Earth equal to the speed of light, its observed speed will be equal to 0.5 s (half the speed of light), that is, 2 times less than in reality.
<i>The observed path traveled by a moving body</i>	
With the true speed of approach of the spacecraft to the Earth equal to 0.5 s its observed path traveled per day (month or year) will be 2 times longer than it actually is.	With the true speed of the spacecraft moving away from the Earth equal to the speed of light, its observed path traveled per day (month or year) will be 2 times less than in reality.
<i>The rate of processes occurring on a moving body</i>	
<p>With the true speed of approach of the spacecraft to the Earth equal to 0.5 s all processes occurring on the body will be observed as ongoing 2 times faster than in reality.</p> <p>In this case, the second hand of the ship's clock, according to observations, will move 2 times faster than the second hand of the earth clock.</p> <p>For 1 second (minute) according to the earth clock, according to the observed readings of the ship's clock, 2 seconds (minutes) will pass.</p>	<p>With the true speed of the spacecraft moving away from the Earth equal to the speed of light, all the processes occurring on the body will be observed as running 2 times slower than in reality.</p> <p>In this case, the second hand of the ship's clock, according to observations, will move 2 times slower than the second hand of the earth clock.</p> <p>For 1 second (minute) according to the earth clock, according to the observed readings of the ship's clock, 0.5 seconds (minutes) will pass.</p>
With the true speed of the spacecraft approaching the Earth equal to 0.5 s, all movements of the astronauts on the video image transmitted from the spacecraft, taken with a frame-by-frame video	With the true speed of the spacecraft moving away from the Earth equal to the speed of light, the movements of the astronauts on the video image transmitted from the spacecraft are observed to be 2 times slower than in reality.

<p>camera, will be observed 2 times faster than in reality.</p> <p>The speech rate of the astronauts on the video image transmitted from the spacecraft will be 2 times higher than the usual rate of speech (as on a fast-moving video file).</p> <p>The cosmonauts' breakfast, which actually takes 20 minutes, will pass in just 10 minutes on the video image transmitted from the spacecraft.</p> <p>During the year that has passed on Earth, on the video image transmitted from the spacecraft, the astronauts will become 2 years older.</p> <p>For 20 years on Earth, on the video image transmitted from the spacecraft, astronauts will age by 40 years. At the same time, in fact, astronauts will age in the same way as people on Earth, that is, by 20 years.</p>	<p>The speech rate of the astronauts on the video image transmitted from the spacecraft will be 2 times slower than the usual rate of speech (as on a slow-motion video file).</p> <p>The astronauts' breakfast, which actually takes 20 minutes, will last 40 minutes on the video image transmitted from the spacecraft.</p> <p>In the year that has passed on Earth, the video image transmitted from the spacecraft will make the astronauts older by only half a year.</p> <p>In 20 years on Earth, on the video image transmitted from the spacecraft, astronauts will become older by only 10 years. At the same time, in fact, astronauts will age in the same way as people on Earth, that is, by 20 years.</p>
<p>rotating at 60 revolutions per minute will be observed rotating 2 times faster, that is, at a speed of 120 revolutions per minute.</p>	<p>An electric motor rotating at a speed of 60 revolutions per minute on a ship will be observed rotating 2 times slower, that is, at a speed of 30 revolutions per minute.</p>
<p>If we observe (hypothetically) through a telescope an asteroid that is approaching us from space at a speed of 0.5 times the speed of light, while rotating around its axis with a true rotation rate of 1 revolution per second, the rotation speed observed through the telescope will be 2 revolutions per second. second, that is, 2 times the true rotation speed.</p> <p>According to observations through a telescope, all processes occurring on the asteroid will flow 2 times faster than in reality.</p>	<p>If we observe (hypothetically) through a telescope an asteroid that is moving away from the Earth at the speed of light , while rotating around its axis with a true rotation speed of 1 revolution per second, the rotation speed observed in the telescope will be 0.5 revolutions per second, that is, in 2 times less than the true rotation speed.</p> <p>According to observations through a telescope, all processes occurring on the asteroid will flow 2 times slower than in reality.</p>

About the Doppler effect

Despite the mathematical similarity of the law of aberration with the Doppler effect, a number of the ratios of physical quantities included in the law (distance to a moving body, body

speed, and others) have nothing to do with the Doppler effect. The Doppler effect expresses the relationship between the frequency (wavelength) of the radiation perceived by the observer (receiver) and the frequency of the radiation source as it moves relative to the observer. The Doppler effect is associated with sound and light vibrations perceived by the observer. A number of physical quantities included in the law of aberration are not associated with oscillatory and wave processes, the relationship between these observed and true quantities, apparently, cannot be derived from the Doppler effect.

The law of aberration is not a generalized Doppler effect.

Experimental confirmation of the reliability of the law of aberration of the physical quantities of the body

An experiment confirming the invariance of the true readings of a moving clock was carried out from November 1999 to October 2014. at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in Boulder, Colorado. In the course of this experiment, scientists observed the course of the frequency standards used by leading metrologists at NIST , as well as in laboratories in the USA, France, Germany, Italy and the UK [22-24].

The 12 most accurate clocks in the world have been observed for more than 14 years. These clocks are located motionless at points at different latitudes of the globe, which move around the earth's axis with different linear speeds equal to

$$v = \cos \varphi R_3 \Omega,$$

where φ is the latitude of the location of the clock;

R_3 is the radius of the globe;

Ω is the angular velocity of the Earth's rotation, rad/s.

During the experiment, it turned out that all the observed clocks ran exactly the same for 14 years, despite their different linear speeds around the Earth.

This experiment convincingly proved that the true course of the clock does not depend on the speed of its movement.

The second experiment confirming the validity of the law of aberration was carried out in St. Petersburg in 2022. During the experiment, the observed rate of the moving clock was measured. In accordance with the results of the experiment, the clocks moving towards the observer according to observations go faster than the stationary ones, and the clocks moving away from the observer according to the observations go slower than the stationary ones [18]. The experiment confirmed the validity of formula (3.22).

Practical significance

A number of inventions have been made using the law of aberration [6 p. 394-416; 25-26], which confirms its high practical significance for solving problems in astronautics and aviation. For example, using the law of aberration, a method has been developed for determining the location of objects using a global navigation satellite system using only two navigation satellites instead of four in the traditional way. This method will make it possible to create promising more accurate, reliable and noise-immune satellite navigation systems.

Received patents for inventions also confirm the validity of the formulas of the law of aberration, since inventions are made using the formulas of this law.

Discussion of the law

The law of aberration was discussed with about two hundred scientists, including candidates and doctors of physical, mathematical and technical sciences.

None of the scientists who discussed the law of aberration could point out any errors and inaccuracies in the derivation of the relations of the law.

This indirectly confirms the validity of the law of aberration.

The beauty of the law of aberration indirectly confirms its reliability

Many of the laws written in mathematical form are beautiful.

The law of aberration of the physical quantities of a moving body is beautiful, both in form and in its physical meaning (in content).

The beauty of the law of aberration indirectly confirms its validity.

Conclusion in several different ways confirms the validity

Some formulas for the law of aberration are derived in several different ways, all of which lead to the same result. This also confirms the validity of the law of aberration and the truth of its formulas.

Even schoolchildren understand the law of aberration. The simplicity of the law of aberration confirms its validity.

Most of the discovered laws of nature are simple. Some elements of the law of aberration in the popular scientific presentation are understood even by high school students of educational institutions. This suggests that the law of aberration is simple, and simplicity is objectively inherent in physical laws. The simplicity of the law of aberration is an indirect sign confirming its reliability.

Conclusion

Thus, in this section, the concepts of aberration of the location and physical quantities of a moving body, the concepts of the observed and true location of the body, and the observed and true physical quantities of the body are introduced.

A discovery of a previously unknown physical law of aberration of physical quantities and the processes occurring on it has been made, which is formulated in mathematical form. The law of aberration covers 16 physical quantities, but it is possible that this number will be increased in the future.

In this work, the law of aberration is presented in a particular case, when a body moves along a line connecting the body and the observer. In the future, it is planned to publish a generalized law of aberration, in the general case of body motion in an arbitrary direction relative to the observer.

Considered polyhedral symmetry, the mathematical beauty of the formulas of the law of aberration.

The open law of aberration of physical quantities is, apparently, due to its many-sided symmetry, one of the most beautiful laws of physics.

The popular scientific presentation of some aspects of the law of aberration is understood even by high school students of educational institutions. This suggests that the physical meaning of the law of aberration is quite simple and understandable to people not only with higher education, but also with general education. Some aspects of the law of aberration are likely to be understood by people even with a basic education.

Obviously, the discovery of the new law of aberration of the physical quantities of the body presented in the work is a significant event, both for modern physics and for science in general.

Feedback and suggestions on this work please send by e-mail. mail: al.plyasovskih@yandex.ru

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